

SATISFACTORY

Project Acronym: **SatisFactory**
 Project Full Title: **A collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem for increasing satisfaction and working experience in smart factory environments**
 Grant Agreement: **636302**
 Project Duration: **36 months (01/01/2015 - 31/12/2017)**

DELIVERABLE D2.4 HR Workload Management Toolkit

Deliverable Status: **Final**
 File Name: **SatisFactory-D2.4-v2.0.pdf**
 Due Date: **June 2017 (M30)**
 Submission Date: **June 2017 (M30)**
 Task Leader: **ISMB**

Dissemination level	
Public	X
Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement n°636302

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Version	Author	Date	Status
0.1	Vergori Paolo	April 13, 2016	Initial Draft
0.2	Morello Michele	May 20, 2016	Draft
0.8	Vergori Paolo	July 21, 2016	Quality Check
0.9	Vergori Paolo	August 5, 2016	Final Draft reviewed
1.0	Vergori Paolo	August 29, 2016	Ready for submission to the EC
1.1	Nadir Raimondo	June 10, 2017	Second iteration
1.2	Riccardo Toppan	June 16, 2017	Partners contribution
1.9	Paolo Vergori	June 20, 2017	Second iteration Final Draft reviews
2.0	Paolo Vergori	June 27, 2017	Ready for submission to the EC

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LIST OF DEFINITIONS & ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
AR	Augmented Reality
CAM	Context-Aware Manager
GCRM	Gesture & Content Recognition Manager
HR	Human Resource
HRM	Human resources management
I-DSS	Integrated Decision Support System
MCDM	Multi-criteria decision making
MQTT	MQ Telemetry Transport
PAP	Personnel Assignment Problem
SAS	Smart Assembly Station
SFP	Satisfactory Platform
UC	Use Case
WP	Work package
WSPM	Work Schedule Prioritization Module

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present document is a deliverable of the SatisFactory project, funded by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD), under its Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation program (H2020).

The deliverable D2.4 describes in details the outcome of the activities that have been performed in Task 2.4 to achieve the development and deployment of the HR workload management toolkit. This document is at its first iteration and is submitted at M20. A refined version is expected at M30 and it will be in its final form.

The first part of the document is an in-depth analysis of the State Of The Art, where the results of a complete analysis are presented. Moreover, a technology exploration overview is also described in order to provide a comprehensive overview of similar tools already in use by technologically advance manufacturers.

The second part foresees a holistic approach and brakes down the implemented functionalities in three sub-categories:

- the visualization map and the information available for supervision of activities at the shop floor level;
- the work schedule view, where information about current and planned tasks are presented to supervisors in a seamless manner;
- the incident replay video view, where information about footage of recorded incidents are presented for further investigation, provisioning video enrichment capabilities.

In order to describe the aforementioned functionalities in a coherent way, a subset of the standard used in D2.1 has been adopted, in specific IEEE 1471 "Recommended Practice for Architectural Description for Software-Intensive Systems" [IEEE 1471, 2000]. For each component is presented the Functional view, the Sequence diagrams and the Class Diagrams. Furthermore, a functional correlation to the addressed use cases is also provided.

The document proceeds analyzing the work schedule management toolkit and the dynamic real-time human resource scheduling engine. The former is deeply integrated with the SatisFactory Decision Support System and all its functions and interfaces are described. A fine detailed overview of APIs interfaces is also present in this chapter. The latter module is a software module dedicated to automatic re-adaptation of existing facilities and workplaces. In its dedicated chapter, this software component is broken down reaching a very fine grained level. In particular, the processing of static and dynamic parameters coming from the shop floor level is described and the algorithmic approach used to analyse them is also in-depth depicted.

Finally, in the document also provides a tangible description of how all the involved components have been tested and deployed in CPERI activities at M15 and in the SUNLIGHT and COMAU pilot sites at M26.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 PURPOSE, CONTEXT AND SCOPE OF THIS DELIVERABLE

This deliverable describes the Toolkit for Re-adaptation of existing facilities and workload balancing to be deployed within the SatisFactory ecosystem. It is worth mentioning that the feedback from both the end-users and workers (due the pre-pilot and pilots installation) has been taken into account during the course of the project to refine the software components and provide a better experience on the field.

Within the SatisFactory work package (WP) structure, Task 2.4 named Toolkit for Re-adaptation of production facilities and HR workload balancing is responsible for design and develop a novel toolkit to increase the efficiency of the production facilities, facilitating the monitoring and supervision in real time of the evolving production processes.

1.2 BACKGROUND

The SatisFactory Platform (SFP) aims to make traditional factories more attractive, supported by continuous training of their employees, stimulating team interactions and capitalising the created knowledge and experience in every level of their organization. Going into details, the SFP collects, aggregates and analyses real-time data from heterogeneous sensors, privacy preserving infrared and depth cameras deployed in the shop floor, interacts with Augmented Reality (AR) glasses and novel HMIs through a fundamental component that is the Middleware. In order to distribute the gathered knowledge efficiently and improve the well-being of both the employees and organization, three main tools are considered, namely, an integrated decision support system (I-DSS), a real-time training environment and finally an independent, pervasive data communication network. Additionally, the SFP addresses workers' safety through proper context aware modules, monitors the production facilities for detecting flaws and problems, and triggers re-adaptation as means for rectifying anomalies and improving throughput. Finally, in order to present all the above information and control capabilities, intuitive and easy to use interfaces, among them AR environments are used. Gamification methods are applied for motivating workers for unpopular tasks.

The SFP will be demonstrated in three different pilots belonging to the three end users (i.e., COMAU, SUNLIGHT, CERTH), where each one targets at different aspect of the operation and activities.

1.3 DOCUMENT STRUCTURE

This document is structured as follows. Section 2 introduces the state of the art analysis for more comprehensive overview of cutting edge technology products in this market segment. Section 3 presents an overview of the different components that create a high level logical toolkit for in factory enhancement model of the production environment.

In Section 4 and 5 in-depth components are technically overviewed and explained to provide an overall documentation for the software that have been developed within Task 2.4 of SFP.

Section 6 will present the conclusion of this first iteration of the components and will lay the foundation for the future development.

2 STATE OF THE ART ANALYSIS

2.1 INTRODUCTION

In the last years the interest in resource management has been increased since optimized utilization of resources has the potential to reduce the operating cost and increase performance and productivity. Optimal management of resources in enterprises/companies, and especially in dynamic environments such as shop floors, is a great challenge as various factors have to be taken into account and unexpected events are possible. Examples of such real-time events include machine failures, arrival of urgent jobs, due date changes, changes in job processing time etc. [26].

The two main types of resources that have to be managed in industrial environments are machinery resources and human resources. These resource types have different characteristics. Machines are subject to unexpected failures and their performance is characterized by low variability. On the contrary, the performance of an employee when executing a task depends on various parameters such as the experience level, skills, time of the day etc. Furthermore, workload balancing among employees is vital to ensure fairness and increase the satisfaction of all employees. It is noted that human resource management (HRM) actually includes task design and analysis, scheduling and workforce selection and allocation, training, performance assessment, even recruitment, legal and ethical issues.

Personnel assignment is a subset of HRM covering mainly performance management and workforce planning and its scope is the placing of right people in the right task. When a team's workload is unbalanced, frustration, dissatisfaction and team conflicts can result, as well as production issues such as under-productivity by some, over-productivity by others and missed deadlines. In some cases, mental and physical stresses and fatigue caused by an unbalanced workload can cause frustration and have an impact on the personnel's health. To prevent these issues, rebalance the workload on a regular basis is necessary by assessing the situation thoroughly and involving the team in helping the leader to determine how to optimally divide the work. A proposed solution is to consult with the project team and discuss the reasons of imbalance, ask for proposed solutions, review the resumes, take into account the experience of each employee and reassign tasks [4]. Additionally, frequent meetings with the team are proposed so as new imbalances to be detected in early state. However, this approach seems out of scope for large industries where the number of employees and the complexity of the production lines is high. Hence, it is necessary to develop and use automated tools to simplify and monitor this procedure.

A resource assignment algorithm deals with the assignment of resources by selecting the most suitable from the ones available and by taking into account resource constraints. On the other hand, a scheduling algorithm assigns resources to tasks while setting the execution starting time of tasks as well. Depending on the execution phase, resource allocation can be static or dynamic. In the former case a set of tasks and a set of resources are available at design time and the allocation of resources is decided before the execution starts. On the contrary, dynamic resource allocation is performed when a new task arrives at run time.

A thorough review of the literature on human resource scheduling problems is presented in [25]. The authors identify trends in research on personnel staffing and scheduling, and indicate areas subject to future research. For example, many characteristics of the human resource scheduling problem that appear in real-life are often disregarded. Thus, it would be useful to integrate as many aspects as possible, such as different skills etc. Literature review also showed that although the majority of the proposed approaches are evaluated using real-world data, the number of approaches that are applied in practice is limited. The two most studied application areas in the literature are the nurse scheduling problem and personnel scheduling in call centers. In the past years, the research attention in personnel scheduling applied to manufacturing and industrial companies has been increased due to the utilization of multiple information sources available via the IT infrastructure. The typical HR scheduling problem for factories involves non-overlapping shifts. Thus, the goal in this case is to assign the work to employees working on each shift.

Saadat et al. [20] present an overview of the research in allocation of human resources within manufacturing shop floors. The authors highlight that the major challenge in workforce allocation is the occurrence of disturbances that are critical in labour intensive manufacturing industries. They also discuss the recent developments in workforce allocation using intelligent systems and refer to a model which is based on holonic manufacturing principles.

2.2 OVERVIEW ON EXISTING TOOLS

As the technological progress advances, factories become more and more complex organisms. Factory organization and supervision not only require a very efficient management of the workers. A constant awareness of the machinery working status becomes a crucial value in order to assess the wellness of a factory as a whole. The number and the complexity of machinery are constantly increasing and the human-machine interaction becomes more and more complex. This makes it harder tracking unexpected events and discovering processing flaws. Industry has then a growing need of rethinking the control and supervision processes with new tools which should be able to effectively interface the production actors with the management levels.

2.3 VISUALIZATION TOOLS FOR SMART FACTORIES

State-of-the-art visualization tools guarantee a close monitoring of the production processes facilitating the detection of deviations from the original working plans. By exploiting innovative tools which provide graphical visualizations of the factory plant, a heterogeneous set of data can be presented in a way which may be easily and immediately understood. As a mere example, by changing the colors adopted to show a machine on a monitoring display, it is possible to understand at a glance whether it is properly working or not. Showing real-time position of personnel inside the facility would enable a promptly identification of possible delays, get an insight of the possible causes, and predict future inefficiencies.

The so-called “Industry 4.0” is in an early stage of evolution. The availability of off-the-shelf visualization tools at present is relatively limited and it is struggling to grow due to the high

fragmentation of the system. The automotive industry has been a forerunner in installing some innovative technologies and this industry has usually adopted proprietary and highly-customized solutions tailored on its specific needs. The market mostly offers semi-custom solutions tailored on specific needs, with very low flexibility and high costs due to the effort needed to re-adapt and customize the tools.

The manufacturing industry, on its turn, is currently adopting many different software tools when addressing its managing processes. Each of these tools usually focuses on specific aspects on the production line so a large set of software applications are installed in a factory in order to satisfy all the different management needs. Commercially speaking, currently available tools can be grouped into four main categories:

- *Human resources management* which addresses man and work scheduling;
- *Mobility workforce management* which addresses the optimization of workers outside the factory premises e.g. the optimization of commercial fleets;
- *Facility monitoring* which focuses on the analysis of the physical status of machinery (in terms of temperature, workload...)
- *Process Management* which addresses order processing and production line optimization.

2.3.1 Human Resources management

One of the key aspects of smart factories is an efficient work schedule management. It is a management aspect which is common to almost all businesses so the market offers many tools to effectively achieve this objective. These tools not only offer the opportunity to manage the task scheduling and workload balance of the employees but they also provide optimization suggestions to achieve both money and time saving. The graphical user interfaces of these tools usually provide an immediate understanding of the employees' tasks workload. The software view is therefore often organized as a GANTT graph. An example of a well-known and widely-adopted human resources management tools is the SAP Workforce Scheduling shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 SAP workforce scheduling.

It can be easily seen in Figure 1 that each employee corresponds to a colored line and this line is divided into chunks representing tasks. Each task has a specific start and end time. Colors and symbols immediately communicate to the user useful information about the tasks to be performed and the interconnections between them.

These tools are usually limited to the specific job they are meant for, without interfacing and exchanging data with other factory tools. The tools can organize work scheduling and optimize the correspondent effort but they usually do not make use of other data a modern factory can provide. As an example, these tools can not automatically react to unexpected events and do not usually suggest real-time work re-scheduling.

2.3.2 Mobility workforce management

Current visualization tools for mobility workforce management focus on offering optimization tools to efficiently manage workers distributed over a large region and not only inside the factory's premises. This means that the visualization tools are developed with the key objective of enabling supervisors to keep track of employees outside the facility, leveraging on map services (e.g. Google maps) to graphically show their location over a wide area. An example is SmartView by ClickSoftware. A screenshot of this tool is given in Figure 2. This software provides details to compare odometers, GPS and Google suggested miles. It is possible to view routes driven by the mobile workers and compare them with the suggested routes. Additional features include reporting details of mileage driven.

Figure 2 Click Software Smart view.

2.3.3 Facility monitoring

Two main categories of facility monitoring can be currently identified on the market. The first category concentrates on monitoring *environmental* parameters inside the factory and the second one on monitoring *machinery and production line* status.

In the first case, the information coming from the shop floor is collected from a grid of sensors and displayed together with geo-localization information on a map of the factory plant. This enables the supervisor to rapidly connect a notification with the hot-point that generated it and then perform the proper actions to solve the issue. An example is RLE's FMS Facilities Monitoring System shown in Figure 3 where floor shop temperatures and anomalous situations are displayed.

Figure 3 RLE's FMS Facilities Monitoring System.

In the case of machinery and production line monitoring, the tools usually show a virtual representation of the production line, displaying information coming from the machinery and, if possible, enabling the user to directly send commands to the machinery. Figure 4 shows an example of a control panel for a glassworks developed by DeltaProgettazioni.

Figure 4 Industrial monitoring panels designed by DeltaProgettazioni.

2.3.4 Process management

Process management is a significant aspect in modern smart factories. The objective of a process management tool is to provide the supervisors with a detailed understanding of the processing level of completion of each order inside the factory. These tools usually have a real time interface which provides information on product placement and production status, enabling the user to check the processing status of a specific order and intervene to solve issues that are blocking or slowing down a specific order or production. A real time interface may allow displaying notification coming from the production line thus empowering the user with the ability to timely solve these issues.

Figure 5 A model of the production line with product localization.

Figure 5 shows a tool which allows to efficiently modeling the production line and it also allows performing product localization inside the factory. The user is able to navigate or search the product list and retrieve specific product information either through the side bar or directly in the model. It is important to note that most of the times these tools are customized solutions tailored on specific factory needs and they are usually adopted only in highly automated production lines.

2.4 HR RE-ADAPTATION IN SMART FACTORIES

The result of the high interest in scheduling and resource assignment, especially in the case of human resources, is that there are numerous studies in the literature proposing different approaches to deal with the above-mentioned problems. Wibisono et al. [27] propose an on-the-fly human resource allocation method in Business Process Management Systems which is based on Naïve Bayes model. Klosowski et al. [15] propose a method for the proper selection of human resources in enterprises which is based on Petri Nets. They define three

objective functions which require simultaneous optimization: the average cost of direct handling, manufacturing capacity and manufacturing cycle. The parameters of the model include the role types, the links between roles and workstations etc. Simulation experiments with different parameters were conducted. A mechanism in which the dynamic resource allocation optimization problem is modelled as Markov decision processes is proposed by Huang et al. [14]. The mechanism observes its environment to learn appropriate policies which optimize resource allocation in business process execution. Cabanillas et al. [9] propose a metamodel to define preferences. In that work the human resources are prioritized according to preferences, based on a ranking mechanism.

Recent work on the human resource scheduling problem includes approaches based on multi-agent systems and heuristics. Skobelev et al. [23] have proposed an adaptive scheduling method for resource management in manufacturing workshops, which is based on a multi-agent system. The model includes agent classes such as Order, Worker, Machine and other. Agnetis et al. [2] proposed two heuristics that solve job shop scheduling problems, taking into account also the skills of each employee. Bouzidi-Hassini et al. [6] discuss a new approach to integrate the scheduling of production and maintenance operations. The approach takes into account human resources availability and is based on multi-agent systems for modelling the production workshop. Brucker et al. [7] present mathematical models which cover specific aspects in the personnel scheduling literature and analyse their complexity. They conclude that heuristics which a) assign feasible shifts to employees, b) create flexible schedules which allow task changes, c) and deal with the number of task changes, need to be developed.

Etoundi et al [10] studied the ants' way of working and collaborating and proposed a load balancing method based on Ant Theory. An algorithm based on the Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) is introduced with three components: i) Labour Ants Component: it is the subset of personnel having the same skills and the same potential to be assigned a task, ii) Search Ants Component: It finds idle times and loads that can be reassigned to another individual and iii) Load Balance Ants Component: It updates the schedule of each employee according to the Search Ants Component information.

Niknafs et al. [17] reviewed the Personnel Assignment Problem (PAP) or Human Resource Management (HRM), which in most application areas is known to be a discrete optimization problem, while there are numerous researchers who subcategorize PAP in Combinatorial Optimization problems. Some other researchers consider PAP a two-sided matching problem. The PAP has been a subject of study for the operations research, as well as management science, engineering management, human resources, and organizational behaviour. Each field of research looks at the problem from its own perspective. One of the popular approaches in solving PAP is the use of genetic algorithms because they offer a number of advantages, such as: i) they do not require a comprehensive mathematical understanding of optimization problems, ii) they may incorporate mechanisms to avoid local optimal solution and iii) they are flexible enough to be incorporated with domain dependent heuristics and form hybrid algorithms.

Other approaches to address the issue are fuzzy logics, multi-criteria decision making (MCDM) methods, neural networks, integer programming, particle swarm, artificial intelligence, machine learning techniques and queueing methods. It is worth noting that the approach selected to deal with the personnel assignment problem is often related to the environment where it will be applied. For instance, the use of queueing methods is more common in applications where the same task can be executed concurrently by a varying number of human resources (e.g. call center applications). On the contrary, queueing methods are difficult to be implemented when for example the assignment of human resources to maintenance tasks performed in an industrial environment is of interest. Evaluating solutions for HRM is an expensive and time-consuming task, because the developed systems are usually based on customized knowledge applicable to specific environments. The single phase of knowledge elicitation for building a knowledge system requires a great deal of time and effort. That might be one reason why almost 50% of the validation methods are simulations.

The main challenge in the personnel assignment is to respect all constraints, to minimize overload and to balance workload among employees. Some of the constraints detected by Afilal et al. [1] are:

- Maximum horizon, weekly and daily work hours must not be exceeded
- Average work hours in 12 consecutive weeks must not be exceeded
- Maximum working weekends must not be exceeded
- Employee must not work the entire weekend (Saturday and Sunday)
- Maximum daily extent must be respected
- Minimum daily rest hours must be respected
- Employee can not work in two different sites in the same day
- Employee's maximum working hours should be respected. (Distinction between fulltime and part time personnel)

The method proposed by Afilal et al. [1] is a key performance indicator (KPI) heuristic approach. A list of candidates is formed with all the employees who can be assigned to a specific task without violating any of their constraints. The candidate with the higher KPI is the one that will be selected for the specific task.

Azadeh and Zarrin [3] presented an intelligent framework for productivity assessment and analysis of human resource in a large petrochemical plant. The efficiency and effectiveness of this company's staff are evaluated by considering three concepts including resilience engineering, motivational factors in the work environment and health, safety, environment and ergonomics. The framework is based on using Data Envelopment Analysis for calculating efficiency and one of the well-known Artificial Neural Networks, namely Multi-Layer Perceptron besides an Adaptive Neuro Fuzzy Inference System trained by two evolutionary methods; particle swarm optimization and genetic algorithm for evaluating effectiveness of the company's workforce. Then, the productivity of staff, which is the sum of efficiency and effectiveness, is analysed to determine the unproductive staff as well as the impact degree of each concept on efficiency and effectiveness. The proposed framework can

provide considerable benefits to safety-critical systems, managers and staff e.g., identifying key factors significantly affecting the productivity of HRM.

Moreover, Pape [18] presented a prescriptive framework to prioritize data items for business analytics and applied it to human resources. To achieve this goal, the proposed framework captures core business activities in a comprehensive process map and assesses their relative importance and possible data support with multi-criteria decision analysis.

Additionally, M. J. Brusco [8] presented a bicriterion formulation of the nonlinear worker assignment problem that incorporated both operational and human resource objective criteria. An algorithm for generating the entire Pareto efficient set associated with the bicriterion model was. A small numerical example is used to illustrate the bicriterion model and algorithm. A second example based on a test problem from the literature is also contained in the paper, and a third example is provided in an online supplement. In addition, a simulation experiment was conducted to evaluate the sensitivity of the algorithm to a variety of environmental characteristics.

Resources are the core of manufacturing models. They provide information about the people and equipment that perform activities on the shop floor. Comprehensive representations of equipment are common but human resources are often defined to a very limited extent. Hedman et al. [13] discussed how work-study data can be applied as input to detailed modeling of human manufacturing resources. The purpose is to provide a valid representation of manual work tasks on a shop floor level. If implemented in manufacturing models the valid representation will contribute to improve planning, control and execution of production.

Giret et al. [12] made a state of the art review of sustainable manufacturing operations scheduling. They characterized what can be considered as sustainable manufacturing operations scheduling, and introduced the relevant challenges and issues. Gahm et al. [11] addressed the topic of energy-efficient scheduling in manufacturing companies because sustainable scheduling is attracting increasing amounts of attention from many manufacturing companies and energy is a central concern regarding sustainability and improvement of energy efficiency.

Another perspective is to consider the successful implementation of an ERP system to be influenced by the level of skills and users knowledge to operate it. Saide and Mahendrawathi [21] have offered the mechanism of the process of knowledge transfer from external to internal company during the process of pre-post ERP implementation. Also, their work presents the importance of deploying both formal and informal knowledge transfer mechanisms.

Yu and Hu [28] proposed an integrated approach for the resource allocation problem. The proposed approach combined the voting method and the Lexicographic Goal Programming (LGP) model and takes into account both qualitative and quantitative factors involved in the resource allocation decision process. The voting method is used to determine ratings of the

evaluating goals. LGP models are then applied to determine the optimal allocation based on the ratings and the approach is applied to a real-world resource allocation problem.

As it has been already shown, HRM is a rigorous research field led and advanced by actual end user needs. Thus, it is no wonder that numerous software products are available in the market to aid in the management and scheduling of human resources and to minimize workload. Indicative ones are shown below

1. IBM Kenexa: Multi module software offering Talent Management, Learning and development, Performance Management solutions.
2. Shiftplanning (<https://www.shiftplanning.com/humanresources>) is a multi-module system which among other utilities serve the employee performance management and the employee task scheduling
3. Snap schedule (<http://www.snapschedule.com/Products>) offers a lot of functionalities such as: i) schedule employees hours based on availability, ii) schedule breaks and specific tasks within shifts, iii) reduce labour and overtime costs for increased profitability, iv) graph coverage in real-time for every minute of the day, v) track overtime, on call, and vacation costs, vi) store data securely in the cloud or on premise, vii) remotely access employee scheduling data, viii) comply with labour rules and collective agreements.
4. Oracle manufacturing execution system for discrete manufacturing consists of the MES workstation for operators and the MES supervisor workbench (<http://www.oracle.com/us/products/applications/ebusiness/scm/062099.pdf>). The main characteristics of the system are that it:
 - Provides enhanced shop floor execution capabilities
 - Improves productivity and efficiency
 - Enhances visibility into shop floor processes
 - Manages exceptions proactively

This topic is depicted more in-depth in D7.1 as part of the SWOT analysis.

3 OVERVIEW OF TOOLKIT COMPONENTS

3.1 INTRODUCTION

In this section we describe how the proposed toolkit can effectively improve the overall quality in a factory. We show how the functionalities implemented in the SatisFactory ecosystem can provide significant benefits in terms of machinery and workers' management thus reducing costs due to previously un-notified inefficiencies.

The visualization toolkit provides an intuitive interface which gives the possibility to analyze the factory at a glance. The benefits are manifold as all the notifications, alarms and unexpected behaviors are collected in a single entity. This allows for a prompt reaction to potentially dangerous events and quick re-adaptations of the previously scheduled tasks. Ease of use and system scalability make the proposed approach a forerunner for Industry 4.0.

3.2 FUNCTIONALITIES

3.2.1 Visualization toolkit

The visualization toolkit allows the supervisor to have a look at a glance on the shop floor. It allows supervisors to automatically receive notifications on specific events on the shop floor, schedule works and watch running machinery in a single and highly customizable view. Three views are currently available namely the map view, the work-schedule view and the incident replay view. The first view is in charge of showing the shop floor with both the machinery and the workers. The second view allows to dynamically analyzing the current work-schedule highlighting the interactions between the different actors. The third view allows to quickly watch and re-play past video recordings of events happened in the factory. A detailed description of the above mentioned views is given below.

The current approach implements tools to display the shop floor in real-time including the location of each worker. The information is gathered throughout the SatisFactory ecosystem and displayed in a multi-modality way. Proper processing is performed in order to extract data required to draw the map containing building information and people location. When moving the pointer over smart machinery or workers, further information is displayed by the system thus allowing for a seamless control over a large set of heterogeneous data using a single interface.

Both static and real-time information are provided. The former group contains static machinery location while in the latter group dynamic data coming from the ecosystem such as the machinery work status can be found. Much information can be immediately found on screen while for other detailed information a click on an object may be required.

If further information is needed for a specific workstation, then a window can be brought in view when that workstation is selected. In this panel, generic information about that workstation is shown together with real-time data gathered through the communication

system. A similar view is available when detailed data about workers are required. A panel can in fact display information on a selected worker such as his technical skills, actual status, current task etc...

A notification panel has also been developed in the proposed framework. It is always visible and displays real-time notifications coming from the SatisFactory ecosystem. The notifications are displayed with different graphic accents in order to differentiate priorities such as alerts or warnings. Notifications are shown in a compacted way and can be expanded or deleted.

The visualization toolkit also includes a view to dynamically analyzing the current work-schedule. This view gathers information from the SatisFactory ecosystem and it easily allows understanding the relationship between the different actors of the system. A detailed description is given to the supervisor when further information is required on particular tasks and workers.

Finally, the toolkit allows watching and re-playing past events. This feature allows understanding better why and how incidents happened. This is of paramount importance in all the cases a detailed study of the shop floor is required in order to avoid the re-occurrence of potentially dangerous situations.

3.2.2 Work schedule management toolkit

The work schedule management toolkit provides various functionalities related to the assignment of tasks to human resources. Task scheduling and human resource assignment is applied to both offline and online cases, when creating the initial work schedule and when scheduling new tasks that arrive during the working hours, respectively. In the first case, the initial work schedule of the day / shift is created and the tasks to be performed are assigned to employees, given a set of tasks and a set of available human resources. In the second case, a new task is inserted to the work schedule and assigned to the required employees in real-time by taking into account the characteristics of the new task and the current state of employees. As a result, the work schedule of the shop floor is adapted accordingly.

In order to support the functionalities described above, the work schedule management toolkit implements methods for:

- Task prioritization based on their characteristics and requirements, in order to set the starting time of each task, and by extension the execution order
- Suitability ranking of human resources according to various criteria such as competence, experience, assigned workload, etc.
- Real-time workload monitoring and balancing functionality, for employees belonging to the same group.

3.3 ADDRESSED USE CASES

3.3.1 HR Workload Management / Re-adaptation toolkit

The HR Workload Management toolkit and the Re-adaptation toolkit are involved at several use cases. They provide in a single point of aggregation, heterogeneous information coming from the shop floor that can be used either for notifying users or as input for other toolkits or components the SatisFactory platform. The presentation and visualization of the heterogeneous data into one application is a useful tool for workers, especially for the supervisors and the decision makers who need to have as much information as possible gathered in order to take decisions with the optimal and fastest way.

The following figure shows the Use Cases where the above toolkits are addressed.

Figure 6 Relationship of the toolkit with the Use Cases.

UC-1.1: Process for handling shop floor related information (data acquisition)

UC-1.1 refers to the ability of the involved actors to import and handle shop floor information related to the static characteristics of the asset-machinery-production data as organized at the repository and to modify operating procedures that are implemented at the business scenarios of SatisFactory. The data should be in appropriate format or type supported by the SatisFactory platform.

UC-1.3: Analysis of real-time and historical info from the shop floor

UC-1.3 refers to the functionality of the system to analyze the dynamic data as stored or the online data as the events, procedures and activities are evolving or changing in real-time at

the shop floor. It also refers to the ability of the SatisFactory platform to process the incoming information and to identify meaningful events that will be utilized later by the platform.

UC-3.1: Online recognition of workers' activities

UC-3.1 refers to the ability of the system to detect the activities performed by the analysis of the human behaviour at the shop floor area, using context-aware information or gesture identification as the operations are evolving. The collection of the heterogeneous data from the shop floor from the toolkit provides workers useful information.

UC-3.3: Monitoring and online notification of abnormal events or alarms

UC-3.3 deals with the notification of abnormal events, situations and alarms to the involved actors across all levels of hierarchy at the shop floor. A suitable filtering is performed depending on the originating source and the severity/priority of the identified event or alarm. Depending on the abnormal events, the Re-adaptation toolkit performs the required actions.

UC-4.1: Provide maintenance work plans and actions related to human-centric activities

UC-4.1 is initiated when an actor requests for information related to maintenance or operation activities according to the daily work plan. Work plans are deployed by the system according to a prototype activity and a plan is created based on this prototype. Actors should follow the instructions of the prototype, in every possible case. It is possible to model most of the activities, but there are also activities which are new and unexpected. In this case, the system is capable of adapting to the new demands and overcome the obstacles by re – adapting the prototypes in a suitable manner. The HR Workload Management toolkit handles any new events which can cause any changes to work plan.

UC-4.2: Acquire work schedules and sequence of actions

This UC refers to the functionalities of the system that are responsible the determination of which work schedules or sequence of actions will be provided to the worker that initiated the request through the respective components. The UC, through the toolkits distributes information on which schedule workers have to work for the day (daily changes) and to make this information easily and clearly accessible. The Maintenance Toolkit provides the daily schedule of tasks assigned to each worker, as well as detailed description for each of the task including instructions, schemas and exceptions workers may encounter during the performance of the task.

UC-4.3: Monitoring and decision support of operations and maintenance procedures

UC-4.3 is responsible for the monitoring of the operations and the maintenance procedures at the shop floor. The semantically enhanced functionalities of the Re-adaptation toolkit assist the decision – making process related to the evolving production procedures. The Maintenance Toolkit communicates with the DSS Core. The DSS Core contains all the rules of the decision support system that can be applied. The Maintenance Toolkit, based on these

rules, monitors the machines and schedules maintenance cycles in the most efficient way for the work flow on the shop floor and for the prevention of machine failures.

UC-4.4: Provide workers availability and allocation of resources

UC-4.4 is responsible for the provision of information related to the allocation of the human resources and the workload balance by utilizing online data from the monitoring and online activities. The availability of the resources and the flexibility of their reallocation are considered using a combination of online data and stored information related to the standard or emergency operating procedures that are explicitly defined for each shop floor and activity within the shop floor. The HR Workload Management Toolkit is able to provide the daily task schedule which will be followed during the day on the shop floor. Workers' availability, number of workers on each shift, criticality of the performed tasks are taken into consideration when the HR Workload Management Toolkit creates the schedule. The mentioned criteria are the most commonly used in the toolkit, but depending on the shop floor, more criteria could be chosen to be applied for the toolkit. Due to the fact that some personnel members can be absent on certain days, without prior notification, the toolkit is able to accordingly re-adapt its schedules.

UC-6.1: Provide informative analytics using advanced visual representation

UC-6.1 is responsible for the presentation of information requested by the actors. The UC will use the functionalities provided by the Visualization toolkit for Re-adaptation to present the requested information to the workers and perform the necessary actions. Key Performance Indicators concerning all actors, as well as actions, on the shop floor provide valuable information about the operation of the shop floor. The information contained in the KPIs is used for analysis and extraction of knowledge. Furthermore, the extracted knowledge is applied to create visual analytics regarding all operations happening on the shop floor and the points that need improvement or reconstruction of works.

4 VISUALIZATION TOOLKIT FOR RE-ADAPTATION

4.1 INTRODUCTION

The visualization toolkit for re-adaptation has been implemented as a web application. This choice has been made due to the great number of benefits deriving from such a solution. First, it is extremely flexible. Adding/removing components is straightforward thanks to the modular approach typical of all the web applications. Second, it is a platform-independent solution meaning that a web application guarantees almost zero installation (and migration) costs. The only requirement is a state-of-the-art web browser on the client side. No installation is required on client side. Furthermore, it is device-independent by definition. This is of paramount importance as it allows high flexibility of installation over a very large set of heterogeneous devices. As a mere example, it can run both on a desktop workstation and a tablet thus allowing a supervisor to move in the shop floor while managing users and machinery from the mobile companion device.

The visualization toolkit allows the supervisors to automatically receive notifications on specific events which happen on the shop floor, schedule works and watch running machinery in a single and highly customizable view as detailed in Chapter 3. The supervisor can rely on three different and complementary views to efficiently manage the factory as a whole i.e. the map view, the work-schedule view and the incident replay view. The first view allows the supervisor to have an immediate view of the shop floor as a whole with both the machinery and the workers currently involved. The second view allows to dynamically analyze the current work-schedule, highlighting the interactions between the different actors of the framework. The third view allows watching and re-playing past video recordings of some events considered significant and previously stored in the system.

From an architecture and technological point of view, the visualization toolkit for re-adaptation has two sides i.e. the server and the client side.

On the server side, the components are based on the well-established node.js paradigm. Node.js³ is a JavaScript runtime essentially built on Google Chrome's V8 JavaScript engine. It is based on an event-driven, non-blocking I/O model that allows for very effective and light implementations. As an asynchronous event driven JavaScript runtime, node.js is especially designed to build scalable network applications. The server runs Express⁴, a HTTP server to host HTML pages and all the resources required by the ecosystem (e.g. JavaScript libraries, CSS, and images). An internal REST API allows managing client requests such as communications with other Satisfactory modules (CIDEM, Middleware, I-DSS).

³ <https://nodejs.org>

⁴ <https://expressjs.com/>

On the client side, no installation of specific components is required. This is especially relevant in situations where a high number of clients are foreseen. A state-of-the-art web browser is required to interact with the Satisfactory ecosystem. The web client receives traditional HTML5 pages with JavaScript. These web pages are written exploiting the innovative features of the Polymer⁵ project, a cutting-edge implementation of the web components framework. The Polymer library provides the developer with a set of relevant features for creating custom elements in web pages. These features have been used in order to dynamically inject portions of custom code, preserving the compatibility with standard Document Object Model elements.

A high-level view of the visualization toolkit for re-adaptation in the Satisfactory ecosystem is given in Figure 7. The main components and their interactions are shown. The re-adaptation toolkit receives data from almost all the Satisfactory components e.g. the CIDEM, the Digital Andon St, the middleware (LinkSmart and MQ Telemetry Transport –MQTT-), the I-DSS, and the Context-Aware Manager. Most of this information is gathered in order to feed the map view with live and static contents. Data are also received to populate the work schedule view and the incident replay view.

⁵ <https://www.polymer-project.org>

Figure 7 View of the visualization toolkit as part of the Satisfactory ecosystem

The overall structure of the view is shown in Figure 8 and a screenshot is given in Figure 9.

Figure 8 Structure of the shop floor map view.

Two main panels can be seen, namely the *Map* and the *Side panel*. They are always visible and directly accessible by the user.

The *Map Panel* depicts the shop floor's map and displays interactive elements based on the data received by the SatisFactory ecosystem. The structure of this panel is organized into three layers, each of them with different functions. The Map Layer is in charge of retrieving, parsing and displaying the building information by drawing a background image. Over this image, dynamic objects will be drawn e.g. workers and smart stations. After the data have been retrieved, it is converted from gbXML to JSON and then elaborated to extract the data needed to draw the map.

The second and third layers of the *Map Panel* display interactive elements which are immediately accessible to the user. The *Workstation Layer* displays the position and the status of the smart stations on the shop floor. Two different data sources are adopted. One is a static source containing information about the positions of the smart stations and the network configuration. The second one is real time data coming from the SatisFactory ecosystem such as the machine work status. For instance the presence detection and people count data coming from the Gestures & Content Recognition Manager (GCRM) provide information about the ongoing activity in the Smart Assembly Station. Furthermore, the Digital Andon St system deployed in the Smart Assembly Stations can propagate progress update about the assembly stage. Some of this information is directly displayed to the user, while all the others are accessible clicking on smart stations.

Figure 9 Shop floor map view screenshot.

The third layer (called the *Worker Layer* in Figure 8) carries out a task similar to the *Workstation Layer*, addressing the workers on the shop floor. The real time position is provided by the Satisfactory Localization Manager. A full list of information about the workers, provided by CIDEM, are available to the user after a proper selection.

The second panel of the shop floor map view is the *Side panel*. It is made of three subsections, i.e. *Notifications*, *Workstation* and *Workers Panels*. The notification panel is always visible and displays real-time notifications coming from the Satisfactory ecosystem. Notifications can be expanded and it is possible to specify a different color for each type of notification (e.g. alert, warning, generic issue...). The workstation panel is usually hidden and is brought in view when a workstation is selected. Finally the worker panel displays information on a particular worker such as his/her technical skills, actual status, and current task. This panel is hidden by default so that enough space is allowed for notifications. This panel becomes visible when a worker is selected.

4.1.1 Functional view

This section provides the functional view of the architecture components and its interactions with the other Satisfactory components. As shown in Figure 7, the shop floor map view component is part of the re-adaptation toolkit and it receives data from the other actors of the ecosystem. In particular, it receives data referring to the workers and the Smart Assembly Station (SAS) from the CIDEM component together with gbXML and forbidden areas information. The Digital Andon St component sends information about the progress status of tasks. Finally, the Middleware sends to the shop floor map view component positioning data and geo-fencing events in order to correctly draw the shop floor map.

4.1.2 Sequence diagrams

In the followings we describe how the shop floor map view interacts with the other components of the SatisFactory ecosystem. As shown in Figure 10, in order to gather all the significant information to populate the view, this component requests to the CIDEM the gbXML, the list of forbidden areas, the Smart Assembly Stations list and the workers list. It also requests the Service Catalog from the LinkSmart. Finally, it subscribes to notification topics to the MQTT in order to receive up-to-date information of events happening on the shop floor.

Figure 10 Shop floor map view component sequence diagram.

Figure 11 Shop floor map view - User selecting a SAS sequence diagram.

Figure 11 shows the sequence diagram of the operations performed when a user selects a Smart Assembly Station (SAS) to get further details on it. As a first step, the toolkit gets from the Multiple-Media Manager the live video for the selected SAS. Then, it gets from the Digital Andon St its progress status. Finally, the re-adaptation toolkit displays the SAS information together with the live video stream of the desired station.

Figure 12 Shop floor map view - User selecting a worker sequence diagram.

Figure 12 shows the sequence diagram of the operations performed when a user selects a worker to get further details on it. In this case, the re-adaptation toolkit gets the worker information from the CIDEM. When this information has been received, then the toolkit displays them on screen.

Figure 13 shows the sequence diagram for the incident detection notification. In order to receive this notification, the re-adaptation toolkit is required to subscribe to the incident detection topic at the MQTT. This task is performed after the service catalog has been received from the LinkSmart. Once the MQTT has received the subscription request, it replies with an ack. This allows the re-adaptation toolkit to be promptly notified by the GCRM

if an incident occurs. This latter informs the MQTT which, on its turn, forwards a proper message to the re-adaptation toolkit. The notification is then displayed on screen. When the notification is shown on screen, the user can click on it. This action generates a message to the Multiple-Media Manager requesting the video streaming which is then displayed on the screen.

Figure 13 Shop floor map view - Incident detection notification sequence diagram.

4.1.3 Updated functionalities of the Map View

Additional features have been integrated in the toolkit to improve its effectiveness and provide to the stakeholders a better experience. More specifically are added functionalities that allow a dialog with workers and a better safety check during the execution of tasks. The new components of the toolkit are:

- Direct call to a specific working station
- Send notification to the Digital Andon
- Ergonomics detection
- Dynamic forbidden areas

Direct call to working station

The re-adaptation toolkit use the Real Time Communication module to create a connection with the Digital Andon St installed in the working stations. The module is based on the open source WebRTC toolkit EasyRTC that provides a real time video and audio communication, between two heterogeneous devices, over peer-to-peer connections. The WebRTC technology defines mechanisms to provide browser-to-browser communications without require either external or internal additional plugins

The WebRTC to allow the supervisor to start an audio conversation with a working station through the icon on the top right of the re-adaptation toolkit. Before the conversation starts it is possible to choose a specific Smart Assembly Station with which interact.

In order to allow the exchange of the real-time messages the Multiple-Media Manager provides to setup the communication session between the peers, where one device must accept or reject the request of connection. After the handshake the browsers exchange audio data without the auxilium of the Multiple-Media Manager central unit.

Figure 14 Incoming call on the re-adaptation toolkit

Even the Digital Andon St can start the communication with the re-adaptation toolkit, where the icon, used to start the audio conversation, notifies the incoming call, as it shown in Figure 14. During the communication the icon changes to indicate that the call is in progress.

A direct communication with the working station improve the management of the works assets allowing to speak to the personnel within the shop floor.

It is required the integration of speakers audio and a microphone in the setup of each station to provide the input and output audio needed to allow the communication between the supervisor and the employees.

Send notification to the Digital Andon

The supervisor can send customized messages to the Digital Andon. The icon on the top right of the re-adaptation toolkit, near the ones used to call the Digital Andon St, allows to write a short message, up to 40 alpha-numeric characters. The supervisor can choose the type of notification between:

- Information
- Warning
- Alert

Each type has its own index of importance that defines the hierarchy of notifications and requires a specific graphic layout.

Figure 15 Text area to write and send notification

The message is published on the LinkSmart MQTT broker and through the message board the notification is displayed on the Digital Andon

The message board provide a customizable template, composed by a title and a vertical list of text fields, as it shows in the Figure 16. Each new notification received from MQTT is displayed on the upper text field and older messages slid down from the bottom edge.

Every notification sent by the re-adaptation toolkit is displayed on the Digital Andon along with notifications sent by others tool installed in the shop floor.

Figure 16 Digital Andon message board template

Ergonomics detection

Wrong movements and bad posture could compromise the employees' safety in the long term, so the continuous monitoring of the workers detects also the ergonomics conditions.

The UWB-based wearable device used in for the Localization System provides the ergonomics monitoring by tracking the posture of workers when performing their activities thanks to the adoption of the inertial sensor. The inertial sensor selected for Satisfactory integrates a 3-axis accelerometer, a 3-axis gyroscope, and sometimes a 3-axis magnetometer; these sensors, in particular the accelerometer and the magnetometer, allow the detection of the attitude in three angles: roll, pitch and yaw.

Thus, it is possible to provide some statistics, for example how often the worker bends his trunk and at which angle along a working day through the analysis of the pitch angle detection.

A notification is sent for each potential dangerous movement caused by wrong postures. The message of the notification describes the ergonomic issue and its severity is defined by the type of notification, that could be warning or alert.

Dynamic forbidden areas

As it described before, the re-adaptation toolkit receives the list of the forbidden areas from the CIDEM, with other information like the gbXML, at the initialization in order to draw the map of the shop floor.

During the working day the list of the forbidden areas could change and it is necessary to update this information in the map.

The re-adaptation toolkit subscribes on LinkSmart MQTT the service of the forbidden areas. When the areas are modified the MQTT sent an event that allows to update the map and all the functions related with the forbidden areas.

Workers panel

The workers panel is a feature that has been added after the first deployment and based on the requirements from the end users. The information displayed in this panel are specific to the shop-floor in which the Re-adaptation Toolkit is deployed. These workers information are retrieved from the CIDEM and are part of the workers information of the B2MML specific section (full details in software deliverable D1.4). In the following is provided an example of the workers panel and how it integrates in the overall visual structure of the Map View.

Figure 17 - workers panel

4.2 WORK SCHEDULE VIEW

The work schedule view is a key feature of the visualization toolkit for re-adaptation. It provides an intuitive visualization of the past, current and future tasks. Furthermore, when needed, it gives detailed information about jobs and personnel requirements for each task.

The work schedule plan is received by the Human Resource Engine (HRE) module and, after proper processing, it is shown on screen. This view displays the work schedule using an

interactive timeline diagram supporting intuitive user interaction (pan, zoom in, zoom out, and job selection). The interface gives the supervisor the possibility to visualize details for each selected job in the work schedule, expanding and reducing relevant information.

Figure 18 Work schedule view. (top) full-window view; (bottom) timeline and job details.

In Figure 18 a screenshot of the work schedule is shown. It is worth noting here that it is possible to interact with the work schedule by using a traditional web browser as the whole visualization toolkit has been developed as a web application. In the upper part of the figure it is possible to see the timeline with hours, days and the different tasks. In the lower part, the same information is displayed together with further data on the selected task. In the example, the view shows task details (id, level of completion) and the personnel requirements.

4.2.1 Functional view

As shown in Figure 7, the work schedule view component is part of the re-adaptation toolkit component and it receives data from the other components of the Satisfactory ecosystem. As an example, the toolkit receives via LinkSmart and the MQTT information about events such as workers' location, virtual geofencing and the current task schedule. In particular, the work schedule view retrieves data from the Human Resource Engine component and provides to the supervisor a snapshot of the current work schedule status in the work schedule view.

4.2.2 Sequence diagram

Figure 19 shows the sequence diagram for the work schedule view. The supervisor interacts with the toolkit using a traditional web browser. HTTP requests are sent by the supervisor to the toolkit server.

The supervisor can request the HTML page corresponding to the desired work schedule view to the toolkit server. The HTML page is then displayed into the web browser and instantiates the two main views i.e. the activity timeline and the task detail panel. This latter is set as hidden by default. The web page asynchronously requests the current work schedule to the toolkit server and downloads it from the Human Resource Engine. The toolkit server validates the work schedule and it can convert it from XML format to JSON format. The result is forwarded to the *ToolkitScheduleView* component.

Once the work schedule has been loaded in the activity timeline widget, the user interacts with it using intuitive conventional interfaces (mouse and touch) to pan, zoom, select and deselect portions of the schedule.

If a task is selected, then the activity timeline sends the correspondent task object to the *ToolkitJobDetailPanel* that displays all the information including description, timing, priority level and different types of requirements. When a task is deselected, then the *ToolkitJobDetailPanel* is hidden in order to make more room to the activity timeline.

Figure 19 Sequence diagram for the work schedule view.

4.2.3 Updated functionalities of the Work Schedule View

The final version of the work schedule view adds subsequent interface improvements to allow the visualization of a fully comprehensive timeline containing both the historical information, from CIDEM, and the daily work schedule provided by the Human Resource Engine. Furthermore, the application has been modified to be compliant with the Business To Manufacturing Markup Language (B2MML) XML schemas adopted by the Human Resource Engine.

Figure 20 shows the improved user interface and new features available for work schedule management.

Figure 20 Work Schedule view

The menu on the top part of the interface enables supervisor to select the activity periods that will be displayed in the timeline panel. After the update request, the toolkit retrieves from CIDEM all the work schedules available in the selected time interval and display the corresponding information. Each work schedule, according to B2MML schemas, is composed by a list of different work requests. These requests are highlighted in orange in the interface. Each work request can further be split in one or more jobs that are displayed with light blue color.

When an update event is received from the Human Resource Manager, through the LinkSmart MQTT broker, the interface is automatically refreshed. The most recent work requests are highlighted in green for an easy identification.

The sequence diagram of the update process is detailed below:

Figure 21 Work schedule update sequence diagram

By clicking a specific work request the user can fit the interface view on the correspondent job list. All the others user interactions, described in the previous sections, to manage the timeline (pan, zoom, move, etc.) are still available in this last version of the software.

Furthermore, the job detail panel requirement sections have been extended to cope with the new information provided by the B2MML schema. In Figure 22 a screenshot of the personnel requirements is shown.

Figure 22 Job detail panel

4.3 INCIDENTS REPLAY VIEW

This view is in charge of providing useful video information about situations occurred on the shop floor in the past. The objectives of this view are manifold, ranging from keeping an historical trace of the status of the shop floor to providing useful elements in order to understand why and how an incident occurred. As for all the other views, it runs in a traditional web browser and this guarantees a high portability both in terms of device and operating system. The size of this view dynamically adapts to the screen resolution. Current tests have been carried out using Apple Safari, Microsoft Edge and Google Chrome web browsers.

Figure 23 shows a screenshot of the incidents replay view running in Google Chrome under Ubuntu. The most part of the view is devoted to display the selected video. A traditional video bar allows stopping and replaying the video, and jumping backward and forward. The list of available videos is displayed on the right side of the screen, with the video currently being played clearly highlighted. Finally, a button on the top-right side of the video allows the supervisor to open a window which gives further information on the video played back.

Figure 23 Incidents replay view.

4.3.1 Functional view

As shown in Figure 8, the Incidents replay view component is part of the re-adaptation toolkit. It receives and parses information received from the Context-Aware Manager and in particular from the Multiple-Media Manager Component. This latter sends a list of the available video content to be displayed, the user clicks on the desired content and this view displays it on the screen.

4.3.2 Sequence diagram

Figure 24 shows the sequence diagram for the incidents replay view. The supervisor interacts with the system using a traditional web browser thus raising an HTTP GET for this view. Once the page has been loaded, the *IncidentReplayView* component interacts with the Multiple-Media Manager via the ToolKit Server in order to retrieve a list of the available video contents. When the supervisor asks for a video, then a request is forwarded to the Multiple-Media Manager via the server. The Multiple-Media Manager replies with the desired video data.

Figure 24 Sequence diagram for the incidents replay view.

4.3.3 Updated functionalities of the Incident Replay View

In the incident replay view is added a button that allows the supervisor to reach the information about the selected video. Figure 25 shows the windows containing three types of information:

- Incident information
- Tags information
- Tags position

Figure 25 Additional information about the stored incident videos

The incident information section reports the ID of the current video, the ID of the working station where the incident occurred, the source of the video and the date of the event.

In the tag information it is shown a list of all the employees detected in the working station during the incident. For each worker it is available the ID of the subject, his distance from the working station and the information about his localization in a forbidden area.

The tag positions displays the map situation during the incident, showing the forbidden areas, the working machine involved and the position of the workers detected. The representation of the employees on the map is red for subjects involved in the accident and it is red for the others.

The list in the tags information and the workers icons in the tags position are linked among them. Selecting a worker in the map the corresponding entry on the list is highlighted and vice versa.

4.4 LOW LEVEL DESIGN

The main goal of this section is to provide a complete class diagram of the major components of the visualization toolkit for re-adaptation along with the role of each class in the system.

Figure 26 shows the class diagram for the shop floor map view. The main class is the toolkit-app that makes use of all the other classes in order to achieve all his different functionalities.

The **toolkit-map** class is in charge of retrieving and parsing the gbXML, the Forbidden Areas List and the Smart Assembly Stations information, in order to draw them on the HTML canvas. It also receives the notifications from the Localization Manager used to display the current workers positions on the map.

The **toolkit-data-refresh** class is responsible of the subscription to all the MQTT topics and the notifications handling, such as parsing and delivering to the correct utilizer.

The **toolkit-notification-list** class is a wrapper for toolkit-list class that incorporate the toolkit-animated-dropdown providing a graphical panel for the deletion of the notifications.

The **toolkit-list** class handles the visualization of all the notifications with different functionalities based on the notifications' type.

The **toolkit-animated-dropdown** class implements a panel with deletion options.

The **toolkit-mjpg-viewer** class is responsible for the fruition of live, deferred and stored videos streams from the Multiple-Media-Manager.

Figure 26 Class diagram for the shop floor map view.

Work schedule view class diagram is shown in Figure 27. The *ToolkitScheduleView* is the main class and it contains two widgets i.e. the timeline and the detail panel.

The class *ActivityTimeline* displays the work schedule in a timeline widget and it guarantees user interaction (pan, zoom in and out, job selection). From an implementation point of view, it is based on the vis.js library⁶, a browser based visualization library designed to handle large amounts of dynamic data, and to enable data manipulation and interaction.

The class *ToolkitJobDetailPanel* displays the details of a selected job. These data can be the title, the description and timing details together with a progress bar. Data also include specific job requirements i.e. personnel, physical, material and equipment. The panel is automatically hidden when no job is selected in the timeline. This class adopts *ToolStackPanel* which is based on *ToolStackItems* to display the requirements' lists.

Figure 27 Class diagram for the work schedule view.

Furthermore, Figure 28 shows the three classes that are in charge of offering the incidents replay view functions. In particular, the *ToolkitVideoList* and the *ToolkitVideoRefresh* address

⁶ <http://visjs.org/>

the visualization and update of the video which can be played back. The *ToolkitIncidentReplayView* class contains these classes and provides the functionalities of video playing and additional information visualization.

Figure 28 Class diagram for the incident replay view.

5 SHOP FLOOR AND PILOTS DEPLOYMENT

5.1 ON THE FIELD TESTS

5.1.1 HR Workload Management / Re – adaptation Toolkit

A preliminary analysis and classification of procedures and individual tasks was performed within the premises of CERTH/CPERI that cover the operations and procedures performed at the shop floor. More specifically the field related activities are categorized to the following:

- Integrated operations
- Individual tasks

A correlation with the groups of actors, and where possible with specific actors, was specified. The selection guaranteed that each type of actor group was included (experienced, novice, trainee).

The following table depicts the preliminary analysis that has been performed regarding the employees, their role and their experience level.

Employee Initials/ID	Role	Experience Level
V.P./ 1	Floor Manager	Experienced
B.S./ 2	Process Supervisor	Experienced
G.N./ 3	Maintenance Manager	Experienced
D.I./ 4	Maintenance Supervisor	Experienced
K.A./ 5	Process Operator	Novice
O.M./ 6	Process Operator	Experienced
M.G./ 7	Process Operator	Experienced
D.S./ 8	Process Operator	Experienced
D.V./ 9	Process Operator	Trainee
M.A./ 10	Electrical Technician	Experienced

Table 1: Analysis of actors' experience level.

After the above analysis regarding actors, an analysis regarding procedures has been performed. The appropriate fields and necessary information was determined. For each group of tasks the following fields have been specified for the needs of the HR Workload balance component:

- Execution order. It shows the order of the specific task within the sequence of tasks of a procedure
- Estimated duration. It is the estimated time that this task will need in order to be completed
- Possible locations. Shows the location where this task will be performed
- Priority level. Shows the priority of the task (Critical, basic or non-critical)
- Required spares, tools to be available. This field is optional and mentions if a spare part or a specific tool is needed for this task.

The following table shows the analysis of the tasks for the BSC-5.1 “Repair or restore Electromechanical malfunction” at the shop floor of CETH/CPERI.

Task/Procedure	Actor	Order	Duration (min)	Possible locations	Priority level	Required spares, (Y/N) to be available
Trace/Identify of the problem	Process Operator	1	5	BIOCAT	Critical	
Verification of the problem and decide the assets and tools that will be used	Process Technician	2	10	BIOCAT	Critical	
Checks the electrical schematics	Electrical Technician	3	10	BIOCAT	Basic	
Checks the state of the alarm	Automation Technician	4	5	BIOCAT	Critical	
Perform actions at the SCADA to allow the repair procedures (and observe the behaviour (result))	Automation Technician	5	20	BIOCAT	Critical	
Perform preparatory actions (eg removes the fuse and respective wiring)	Electrical Technician	6	5	BIOCAT	Critical	

Perform appropriate actions depending on the alarm type (HHI, LOLO) and status of components	Electrical Technician	7	10	BIOCAT	Critical	screwdriver, Multimeter
Restores the components to the proper state at the electrical cabinet (Connects back the fuse)	Electrical Technician	8	10	BIOCAT	Critical	screwdriver
Perform next level tests (Removes the wires of the resistor and measures the resistor)	Electrical Technician	9	15	BIOCAT	Critical	Multimeter, screwdriver
Perform actions to repair the resistance at the cabinet or to reconnect it (If damaged then replace)	Process Technician	10	20	BIOCAT	Critical	screwdriver
Releases the process for normal use	Electrical Technician	11	10	BIOCAT	Critical	
Enables normal state at the SCADA - Starts auto function and gives feedback	Automation Technician	12	10	BIOCAT	Critical	
Verifies that normal operation for a period of time	Process Operator	13	20	BIOCAT	Critical	
Views reports of the task and outcome of the procedure	Maintenance Supervisor	14	5	BIOCAT	Basic	

Table 2: Tasks for BSC-5.1.

The above example involves an integrated approach and the included tasks must be performed in the mentioned order and the procedure will be completed only when all tasks have been successfully completed.

Besides the integrated operation that involved the collaboration of multiple actors there are also individual tasks that can be performed by unique actors with no reaction with other tasks and with no specific order. The following table shows some of these tasks with the related information:

Topology	Task Name	Actor/Role required	Estimated duration	Priority level	Experience level needed
FCC	FCC Level control of Air zero Gas Tanks	Electrical Technician	1 hour	Basic	Experienced
FCC	FCC Horiba filter replacement	Electrical Technician	0.5 hour	Basic	Novice
FCC	FCC Oil WTM-2 Replacement	Electrical Technician	2 hours	Basic	Experienced
Infrastructure	Support of Data infrastructure of the pilot plants - Backup LTO tapes	IT Technician	0.5 hour	Critical	Novice
FCC	Remove and clean trim PV501	Process Technician	0.5 hour	Basic	Experienced
BIOCAT	Open REA701 and D701 cleaning	Process Technician	2 hours	Basic	Experienced
FCC	Maintenance of R101 Injector	Electrical Technician	4 hours	Basic	Experienced
FCC	Resistor 102A stop working	Automation Technician	3 hours	Critical	Experienced
BIOCAT	Replacement of HV85 to High Temperature Valve	Process Technician	1 hour	Non Critical	Experienced
BIOCAT	Configuration of Data exchange service	IT Technician	7 hours	Critical	Experienced
VB01	Change valve seat, cleaning sensor and calibrating MFC	Automation Technician	5 hours	Basic	Experienced
FCC	TE405A temperature lower than Set Point with Analog output opening of TY405 at 100%	Automation Technician	1 hour	Critical	Experienced

HDS	Installation of thermocouple 93	Automation Technician	0.5 hour	Basic	Novice
BIOCAT	Resistance installation on output line of reactor	Process Technician	1 hour	Non Critical	Novice
VB01	SLA5850S Check at Calibration Room. Opens and closes valve according calibration.	Automation Technician	3 hours	Non Critical	Experienced
VB01	Injection with double syringe	Automation Technician	2 hours	Basic	Experienced
BIOCAT	Service actuator at Chromatograph GC215	Automation Technician	2 hours	Basic	Experienced
FCC	Replacement of TSS102A	Automation Technician	1 hour	Critical	Experienced
FCAUTO	Maintain web service for data sharing	IT Technician	1 hour	Basic	Experienced
HYSOLGEN	Hydrogen cylinders change	Process Technician	0.5 hour	Critical	Experienced
HYSOLGEN	Fill-in the water purification subsystem	Process Technician	1 hour	Basic	Novice
HYSOLGEN	Verify electrolysis operation for hydrogen production	Automation Technician	0.5 hour	Basic	Novice
HYSOLGEN	Inverter readapt after failure to pump hydrogen	Electrical Technician	1 hour	Critical	Experienced

Table 3: Individual tasks at CERTH/CPERI shop floor.

For the evaluation of the algorithmic approach and the produced output of the real-time HR scheduling and workload balancing engine, tests were initially performed offline. Data regarding maintenance tasks and employee information provided by CPERI pre-pilot were utilized, as described above. The graphical user interface of the HR scheduling and workload balancing engine, which is shown in the following figure, has been created for reviewing the produced output. The information that is displayed in the user interface includes the work

schedule, which is shown in a Gantt diagram, the assigned tasks per employee, the completed tasks and the availability of each employee. Moreover, additional information is presented in the event log area regarding the decisions that have been made and the changes that have been applied to the work schedule.

After the successful evaluation of the engine in offline mode, the functionality in online mode was evaluated. In that case, the real-time exchange of data with the other components and the communication APIs were tested. More specifically, the HR engine received successfully the initial work schedule, received and processed a new task and finally produced the adapted work schedule. A screenshot of the HR scheduling engine when operating in real-time mode at CPERI shop floor is shown in Figure 30.

Figure 29 Graphical User Interface showing task allocation (offline mode).

Figure 30 GUI of HR scheduling engine when running in real-time at CPERI.

Two different simple case scenarios are presented next for demonstrating the HR assignment functionality. They involve two Automation technicians working on the same shift. Two tasks are initially assigned to Automation technician with ID:14 and one task is assigned to Automation technician with ID:18, as shown in the following figure. A new task (TE405A) of higher priority, which requires an Automation technician arrives at 09:30. Both the technicians are candidates for the task and are available when the task arrives. The task is scheduled to start immediately. The technician 18 is selected due to the lower adaptation cost (0 versus 0.172), as there is no overlap between the new task and his already scheduled task. The total cost of selecting employee 18 is 0.16 while the cost of selecting employee 14 is 0.281.

Figure 31 Scheduling an arriving task in the first scenario.

A different scenario involving the same employees is shown in the following figure. In this case two tasks are assigned to the technician with ID 14, and one task is assigned to the technician with ID 18. A new task of lower priority compared to the ones already scheduled, arrives at 10:30. The new task overlaps with the higher weighted tasks already scheduled and therefore it cannot be started immediately. The algorithm assigned the task to the technician with ID 14 and its starting time was set to 12:00. The selected technician was the only candidate at the specific starting time since the technician 18 was performing a task of higher priority.

Figure 32 Scheduling an arriving task in the second scenario.

In another case, which involves two Automation technicians as well, a new maintenance task of high priority that requires an Automation technician is created at 11:35. The estimated duration of the task is one hour and both the Automation technicians (ID_14, ID_18) are candidates for the task. Their tasks already assigned at the time of the arrival of the new task are shown in Figure 33. It can be observed that when the new task arrives, both technicians are busy: technician ID_14 is performing Task_1, while technician ID_18 is performing Task_2. Due to the fact that the new task is of significantly higher priority, it has to be started as soon as possible which means that the running task will be suspended.

The re-adapted work schedule that the HR engine produced in the case when semantically-enriched information was taken into account, is illustrated in Figure 34. The technician ID_14 was selected to perform the arriving task. More particularly, the suitability score produced from semantic analysis for technician ID_18 was 0.5, while the score for technician ID_14 was 1. As a result, the capability cost of technician ID_14 was significantly lower, and by extension, the total cost of selecting technician ID_14 was 0.27 while the corresponding cost for technician ID_18 was 0.38. The suspended *Task_1* of technician ID_14 was scheduled to be continued after *Task_4*.

Figure 33 Task list of employees before the assignment.

Figure 34 Task list of employees after the addition of the new task.

5.1.2 Interaction with other components

The Re-adaptation toolkit interacts with many components within the Satisfactory ecosystem. In specific, during the pre-pilot activity that has been carried out at M15, it has been tested the interaction with:

- Digital Andon St
- Gestures & Content Recognition Manager
- Multiple Media Manager
- Localization Manager
- iDSS

In the followings are explained what kind of visual information are represented from these components.

In following are briefly explained the interactions with the iDSS. A comprehensive overview can be found in Section 6.1. The real-time HR scheduling engine is integrated with the LinkSmart middleware in order to exchange information with the iDSS and other components. Initially, the current work schedule of the day is received as input form the iDSS in the appropriate XML format. When a new task has to be scheduled during the day, the event containing the task requirements in XML format is received from the iDSS. The HR scheduling engine then retrieves the latest work schedule from the iDSS, performs the necessary calculations and publishes a new event via middleware which contains the updated work schedule of the day in the appropriate CIDEM compliant format.

Digital Andon St

The Digital Andon St is considered to be the visualization part of a module, such as the GCRM and hence, it is part of a hands free assembly assistance module. The Re-Adaptation toolkit gathers the progress update status from the Digital Andon St whenever specific details about a Smart Assembly Station are required by the supervisor. A progress bar is shown underneath the live video feed from the camera.

Figure 35 A screenshot of the Digital Andon St notifications tests.

Gestures & Content Recognition Manager and Multiple Media Manager

From the Re-Adaptation Toolkit perspective the Gestures & Content Recognition Manager (GCRM) and Multiple Media Manager can be considered as a single entity. Despite their tendency of provisioning information as distinctive modules on separate topics in the Middleware and being separate resource in the LinkSmart resource catalog, they can be considered to be one a subset of the other. In specific, the Gestures & Content Recognition Manager provides notifications in respect of specification of the Context Aware Incident Detection Engine (described in D3.3). The Re-adaptation toolkit provides both active and passive incident management counter measures. The former happens in case not all the safety gear is correctly detected and therefore the supervisor is informed by a warning notification, that a worker is operating in an area without the required gears. The latter is triggered when the fall detection engine triggers a fall in the supervised area. In this second case an alert message is dispatched. Furthermore, whenever a maintenance request is detected the Re-adaptation toolkit is notified.

The Multiple Media Manager provides a live video streaming service to the Re-adaptation Toolkit. Moreover, a deferred video service is also available whenever an incident occurs. In the next iteration of this component a video browsing service is available to display historical data based on incident detection and the possibility of semantically enriched video is also taken into consideration for adding information to the supervisor while browsing these media.

Figure 36 GCRM and Multiple Media Manager notifications at CERTH/CPERI shop floor.

Localization Manager

The Localization Manager provides to the Re-adaptation toolkit punctual information about positioning of personnel within the shop floor. As previously described in this chapter the Map View is in charge of display the position in a gbXML contextualize and mapped environment, providing a comprehensive abstraction of the shop floor level to the supervisors. Furthermore, the component dispatches geofencing alert messages that are notified by the integrated notification system.

Figure 37 A worker is moving at the shop floor.

iDSS

iDSS is considered to provide the knowledge and the rules behind the HR Workload Management Toolkit. According to the rules provided and implemented by the iDSS, the daily work schedule is created for the HR Toolkit. Even when there are unexpected and unreported changes iDSS is able to re-adapt the work schedule according to them. Additionally, iDSS provides the system's KPIs, depending on the rule engine and the gathered data. It is noted that the KPIs are selected in collaboration with the end users, so that they are in line with the companies' business objectives. The KPIs are fed to the visual analytics toolkit and graphs, and schemas containing the obtained knowledge are created.

Figure 38: Work Schedule Screen of the HR Workload Management Toolkit

Other SatisFactory components such as the CIDEM, the Middleware and LinkSmart have been exercised during the tests, but since the technical procedures that involved these modules have been explained in detail in the previous subchapters of this document, these have been implied in the description.

Detailed description about the setup and on field tests performed at the shop floor of CERTH/CPERI can be found at Deliverable "D5.3- Industrial lab use case Set-up and Demonstration".

5.2 SUNLIGHT

In order for SUNLIGHT to improve its production facility, several Use Cases and Scenarios must be taken into account. Four BSCs (BSC 3.1, BSC 4.1, BSC 4.2, BSC 4.3) are going to be implemented at SUNLIGHT's two shop floors, the motive power battery assembly line shop floor and the jar formation shop floor. SUNLIGHT aims within its involvement into SatisFactory project, can be summarized into three objectives.

1. **Production activities real-time support:** smart AR interfaces will provide to workers both an overview of their tasks and activities during Their working day, as well as real-time information on changes regarding Their work, such as components to be used, or modification to the amount of cells to be produced.
2. **Events and incidents logging:** Real-time interaction between actors with different roles (workers, supervisors, technicians, managers) has been explored, alongside with various incidents and events.
3. **Learning environment:** SatisFactory modules learning environment is expected to greatly impact on SUNLIGHT production plants, allowing for fast training of new employees and introduction of the workforce to new technologies.

To achieve above described objectives, scenarios involve installation of all SatisFactory project components and their testing plus validation both individually and all together, as a whole.

Installation of most of the components has been already performed. Briefly:

- **CERTH** installed CIDEM, AR In-Factory, Incident Detection, Collaboration and Gamification platform plus the sensors required for Smart Sensor Network implementation (i.e. depth cameras and thermal camera).
- **ISMB** performed installation of Smart Assembly Station, Notification Panel, Gesture & Content Recognition Manager plus Localization Manager components of Context Aware Manager toolkit.
- **Atlantis** deployed Maintenance Toolkit, iDSS and implemented the connection of iDSS with other SatisFactory components, Training Toolkit and HR Workload Balancing Toolkit.
- **FIT** installed LinkSmart Middleware that connects all SatisFactory components.

The HR Workload Balancing Toolkit has been installed by Atlantis, as mentioned above. The testing phase has already begun. Next step is to run the toolkit with real tasks from the shop floors as well as tasks specifically created for the tool.

BSC 3.1 – PREVENTIVE AND CORRECTIVE MAINTENANCE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

SUNLIGHT shop floor production lines operate 24/7. Due to this tight schedule, the avoidance of malfunctions is crucial; it is also important all the heterogeneous operations are performed as smoothly as possible. A Technical / Maintenance Team is responsible for maintaining machinery and equipment. BSC 3.1 goal is to organize Maintenance activities effectively and to improve Technical Department working environment.

Application scenario can be described by following steps:

- Failure event notification
- Action planning
- Work scheduling
- Tasks assignment
- Work execution

- Work completion
- Production of intervention reports

Due to the fact that, the knowledge of the available resources and requirements of each maintenance task is crucial for this scenario, makes the HR Workload Balancing Toolkit the core toolkit of the scenario. The job of the supervisor can be assisted from the HR Workload Balancing Toolkit at every step.

BSC 4.1 – MOTIVE POWER BATTERY ASSEMBLY LINE

4.1 Business Scenario takes place into assembly line for motive power batteries. Once battery cells have been produced, into another SUNLIGHT factory department, next steps involve (i) packing cells into metallic boxes, (ii) connecting cells all together creating a battery string, (iii) installing terminal plugs and water filling system (optional), (iv) checking the need for additional electrolyte, (iv) passing from quality check and (v) putting labels, packing and forwarding to warehouse for dispatch.

The aforementioned production line does not use machineries and almost in every step the procedure is done by hand. If a worker is new, or wants further information about a procedure in the assembly line, She / He may find what She / He needs thanks to the Smart Assembly Station. Information on every procedure and manuals are easily accessible. Access to information needed can be done remotely to Smart Assembly Station engine through the Gesture & Content Recognition Manager component of Context-Aware Manager. Moreover, when using mobile devices like tablets, smartphones or AR glasses, workers can have access to helpful information via Linksmart Middleware.

HR Workload Balancing Toolkit in this scenario helps the supervisor to organize the schedule.

BSC 4.2 – MONITORING OF CELL TEMPERATURE DURING JAR FORMATION AND DATA COLLECTION

The goal is to remotely and continuously monitor the temperature of battery cells during jar formation. Furthermore, it aims to collection and analysis of temperature data. There are 11 jar formation modules covering an area of 1000 m². Now, temperature is measured manually applying a sampling rate of one measurement per hour. Workers, that records the temperature, scan battery cells undergoing formation process one by one. In BSC 4.2 a thermal camera has been installed in order to monitor cells temperature continuously and, as a result, more reliably. Main scope of SatisFactory in BSC 4.2 is to make this procedure more automated and easier for SUNLIGHT workers, plus save man hours and effort.

The main logical flow of BSC 4.2 – monitoring of cell temperature during jar formation and data collection is:

- Identification of condition-based preventive action
- Alarm recognition
- Alarm acknowledgment

- Work assignment
- Work execution
- Work completion
- Production of intervention reports

Since an incident has been detected, HR Workload Balancing Toolkit can be very helpful in this scenario. It is able to inform the supervisor for the incident and also to assist him by informing him for available resources.

BSC 4.3 – TRAINING PLATFORM FOR PRODUCTION PROCESS ON MOTIVE POWER BATTERIES ASSEMBLY LINE

Application Scenario BSC 4.3 refers to the need of a training platform which will help the trainees to understand how to perform their job safely and more efficiently. This procedure includes two parts. The first one concerns the theoretical approach that will provide to trainees needed background on each particular process. In the second part, trainees will receive work training which will incorporate also AR tools, making the process more attractive to the trainees themselves. The platform will also include a trainee evaluation questionnaire which will evaluate whether the trainee has been trained sufficiently or not. BSC 4.3 goal is to develop a training platform to demonstrate production processes to the trainees. To achieve this goal, Augmented Reality platform and devices will be used. Moreover, Satisfactory, through Gamification Framework components, allows trainees and trainers for enriching training material.

BSC 4.3 – training platform for production process on motive power batteries assembly line main operational flow is:

- Identification of training needs
- Determination of training perimeter
- Training delivery
- Training feedback
- Training on the WorkPlace
- Provision of training material

Even if the HR Workload Balancing Toolkit is not been designed for this specific scenario, it is useful for its ability to track the training of each worker suggesting which workers may need to repeat some parts of the training. In the following is provided an image from the SUNLIGHT deployment showing the Smart Assembly Station. The NUC is hidden in the industrial safety box with all wiring under the Digital Andon.

Figure 39 - SUNLIGHT deployment

5.3 COMAU

At M26 ISMB has deployed its component in COMAU shop floor. Therefore, the Re-adaptation toolkit has been installed at this shop-floor premises.

In the followings the list of the modifications required by the end-user to the deployed component after the first on-the-filed evaluation:

- Introduction of privacy-preserving capabilities with mode toggle button at user disposal;
- Iterative visual representation of Smart Assembly Station operational progress;
- Iconographic representation of Safety Gear Detection on Smart Assembly Station status;
- Enhanced notification system for supporting more information coming from connected components from the Satisfactory ecosystem (i.e. ergonomics alerts of sensorized personnel, work schedule update from HR engine);
- Novel worker panel for displaying on-the-go actors details, in near real-time;

- Virtual dynamic forbidden area visualization, for implementing temporary off-limits area at the shop-floor level in particular situations;
- Locale in Italian: enhanced readiness level from expected TRL.

In the following there is a picture of the wiring and the NUC deployed in COMAU in a Smart Assembly Station. We could not provide a broader set of picture from the photo shooting, because of the confidentiality of the environment in which the components are deployed.

Figure 40 - COMAU wiring of NUC

At M31 the first data collection will involve this deployed component alongside all SatisFactory ecosystem. Since this is the last iteration of this document the software described is to be considered as final and the results will be made available in D5.2.

6 WORK SCHEDULE MANAGEMENT TOOLKIT FOR RE-ADAPTATION

6.1 DSS INTEGRATION

6.1.1 Overview

The shop floor is a very intense place for the worker and the supervisor. There is continuous need for decisions on how to implement and schedule repeatedly or not occurring tasks. The supervisor of a specific unit or team is responsible to assign every single task to workers and to decide for the work-schedule and shift in any given day, week, month etc. The aim of the Work Schedule Prioritization Module (WSPM) is to automatically create the daily schedule and to have it available at the beginning of any given day/shift (or at the end of the previous day/shift) to the supervisor.

Figure 41 Distribution of maintenance tasks on Sunlight.

As an example, the above graph locates the number of tasks per asset on the Y axis. The data is provided by the SUNLIGHT shop floor, one of the project's end users, over a period of several months, as they are being monitored within the Satisfactory project. On the X axis, the assets are reported (the Greek language is used due to locale settings in the pilot).

The graph visually indicates that there is a large number of tasks in respect with each separate asset. Every day, implementation of these tasks has to be assigned to various workers. The prioritization process should consider several factors in order to schedule for these tasks. The factors shall be different on each shop floor, hence the toolkit must be

adaptable to each scenario and each company's business objectives. A short, but not exhausting, list of prioritizing factors is:

- Asset criticality
- Task duration
- Worker experience
- Task criticality
- Worker availability

It also provides to the supervisor a way to intervene and change the suggested prioritization, if they desire to do so. The toolkit has been designed in a way that the process of the automatic prioritization may run when the supervisor asks for it, or in a timely fashion (e.g. once per day). Furthermore, the toolkit has been optimally designed so as to exclude tasks that can't be done, due to material shortage, or not suitable equipment available. Additionally, it takes into account the workers' skill, in order to match each task to the suitable/required expertise of worker and experience. The toolkit is able to provide statistics that could be useful to evaluate the workload, the workers' experience, and the condition of assets.

6.1.2 Functions

As it has been aforementioned, the Work Schedule Prioritisation Module, WSPM, provides a tool for automating these everyday decisions and also allows for customisation and changes. The following figure shows the logic and the workflow of the module.

Figure 42 Workflow of WSPM.

The scheduling process runs as described, based on the shop floor layout, the worker skills and status (worker expertise, current experience, worker load) and the tasks at hand. The Work Schedule Prioritization Module feeds this schedule into CIDEM, to which it is compliant.

After that the schedule is available to every Satisfactory component. It is pointed out that DSS provides a graphical interface for having an overview of a specific schedule.

6.1.3 Key Features

The key features for the Work Schedule Prioritization Module (WSPM) are that it is:

- Lightweight

WSPM can run in background and demands very little resources

- Easily integrated

WSPM exposes a variety of services in the form of RESTfull API and can be integrated in various cases.

- Extendable

A variety of configurations is available. Also, DSS is modular, therefore more components could be added when and if needed.

The WSPM is a part of DSSCore, as it can be seen from the architectural diagram below. The DSSCore is deployed as a part of I-DSS WebServer or as a standalone component.

The following figure show the WSPM to be a part of the DSSCore, which is in turn a service in the entire I-DSS WebServer. DSSCore gives a valuable context to WSPM. Specifically, the DSSCore has historical data about previous tasks, or tracks events that may interrupt the schedule.

The WSPM can run in interactive mode as part of MaintenanceToolkit or in integrated mode as service. The interactive mode provides a friendly and graphical user interface for the supervisor to see the results of scheduling or even to change them. On the other hand, in the integrated mode, it can be used in order to integrate the WSPM in a larger ecosystem or in order to extend the standard functionality with different task sources or visualisation toolkits.

Figure 43 I-DSS and Prioritization Module.

6.1.4 Maintenance Toolkit

In the figure below, one can see the list of tasks before the execution of the WSPM. The Toolkit UI has four (4) main areas:

- The toolbar

The supervisor may add or remove tasks, export the current list into excel, and in general interact with the toolkit;

- The calendar (Titled as Schedules Tasks)

It provides the status of a current schedule in a calendar layout;

- The list of workers

It is the list of the available workers;

- The list of tasks (titled as Tasks to Schedule)

It is the tasks that need/remain to be scheduled. These tasks can be new for a certain shift or deferred from a previous day.

Figure 44 Scheduling view.

Scheduling can run automatically (e.g. once a day) or if the supervisors wants to reschedule at any given moment. After that the tasks are re-arranged. It should be mentioned that the supervisor can make additional tweaks if he/she wishes to.

Scheduling the daily tasks in the HR Workload Management Toolkit follows the steps below:

Step	Action
1	Run the Scheduling as an iDSS service in the background
2	Create all the necessary tasks in the HR Workload Toolkit
3	The Scheduling service is able to assign and adapt to work scheduling progress
4	The service shows the tasks on the calendar

Table 4: Action steps for the HR Workload Management Toolkit and scheduling of tasks

When an inferred task, that previously did not exist in the schedule, arrives, the service is able to change the order of the tasks. Depending on the rules that exist in the iDSS, the inferred tasks are assigned to workers according to their criticality, the worker’s experience as well as the overall workload in order both inferred and previously scheduled tasks to be facilitated. Scheduled and inferred tasks are automatically managed and scheduled, as well as shown in the Calendar of the toolkit. It is noted that the supervisor can decide to use the

suggested work program or he/she can manually make changes directly and easily on the calendar view.

The following picture shows how some tasks can be scheduled and how they are shown in the HR Workload Management Toolkit

Figure 45: Tasks after automatic scheduling

The iDSS service runs in the background and is able to re – schedule and adapt the work flow on the shop floor according to different needs in any given moment of the day. A view of the running application in shown in the figure below:’

Figure 46: Re - scheduling of five tasks

6.1.5 *Integrated Mode*

In the integrated mode, the WorkScheduling can be done entirely with service calls in order to support different specialized visualization toolkit. For that purpose, there is an extensive API in D3.5. This API is available through HTTP as RESTfull web-services. Using services the following could be provided:

- The list of tasks
- The list of workers
- Configure the scheduling parameters for an installation.

Prioritization Process

The prioritization process follows the following steps:

- Reading of tasks
The toolkit retrieves the list of open or unscheduled tasks
- Filters out not feasible tasks (due to lack of materials or equipment)
- Calculate the gain and the cost for each task. The cost function is basically the duration for each task. The gain is a weighted sum of selected features.

$$\sum_i^n W_i * F_i,$$

$$\sum_i^n W_i = 1,$$

Where W_i is the weight of feature i and F_i is a score function that evaluates the feature i of a task.

For example, if we schedule tasks according to these two specific features: {AssetCriticality, WorkerExperience} and we have two tasks t1 {'Asset01', 'Expert'} and task t2 {'Asset02, "Novice"} the F_i evaluates as {9, 8} for a task t1 and t2 {7,8} for another. If the weights for the specific case the weights are {0.6, 0.4} then the gain is 8.6 for t1 and 7.4 for t2

- In the last step, the toolkit produces the optimum order for the tasks and the optimum assignment for the tasks. Specifically, for a specific Task set produces the order and assignment that the sum of all gains is maximum.

Figure 47 Prioritization Activity Diagram.

Information (Data)

The list of data used from WSPM for the work-scheduling procedure is given below. The types are a light-weight adoption of B2MML types.

JobOrder

This type keeps information for a specific job. A WorkRequest can include one or more JobOrder types.

Field	Type	Description
ID	String	Unique identifier
Description	String	Job description
WorkType	String	Type of job (e.q. Maintenance, Production)
StartTime	Date	When the job is starting (W3C format)
EndTime	Date	When the job is ending (W3c)
PersonnelRequirements	Personnel	Personnel info for that job
PhysicalAssetRequirements	PhysicalAsset	The asset that job takes place

MaterialRequirements	MaterialRequirements	Any material needed for the job
EquipmentRequirements	EquipmentRequirements	Any equipment needed for the job

PersonnelRequirements

This type keeps information for the works involved in a specific job

Field	Type	Description
ID	String	Unique identifier
Description	String	FullName of the worker

PhysicalAssetRequirements

This type keeps information for the asset

Field	Type	Description
ID	String	Unique identifier
Description	String	Asset description of the job

MaterialRequirements

This type keeps information for the material required

Field	Type	Description
ID	String	Unique identifier
Description	String	Material description of the job

EquipementsRequirements

This type keeps information for the equipment required

Field	Type	Description
ID	String	Unique identifier
Description	String	Equipmentdescription of the job

WorkSchedule

Field	Type	Description
ID	String	Unique identifier
PublishDate	Date	Timestamp of that feed
WorkRequest	List of JobOrder	

6.1.6 API

According to Satisfactory general architecture the WSPM exposes a specific service (available directly or through service catalog) in order to send the schedule tasks to other Satisfactory components. The current version of module exposes the service below that

returns the current schedule. The following data is also pushed to CIDEM for historical purposes.

Title	Schedule <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Fetching the current list of scheduled tasks</i>
URL	<code>/schedule</code>
Method	GET
URL Params	Required: <code>id=string</code> The shop floor id example: <code>id=CPERI</code>
Success Response	Code: 200 Data: WorkSchedule
Error Response	Code: 401 UNAUTHORIZED
Sample Call	<pre>\$.ajax({ url: "/schedule", dataType: "json", type : "GET", success : function(r) { console.log(r); } });</pre>
Notes	<i>WorkSchedule is a type declared into CIDEM</i>

7 DYNAMIC REAL-TIME HUMAN RESOURCE SCHEDULING ENGINE

The real-time automatic assignment of arriving tasks to human resources is addressed by the corresponding scheduling and re-adaptation engine. The goal is to schedule arriving tasks efficiently, taking into account the characteristics and special requirements of each task and the static and dynamic information of each currently working employee. Tasks and employees are the main entities involved in the dynamic task scheduling and HR assignment process. Static and dynamic parameters of both these entities are considered. The utilized inputs, the algorithmic approach and the output are described in the following sections.

7.1 STATIC INPUT PARAMETERS

The static information about tasks that the HR scheduling engine requires is the following:

Task type: Task type is a special ID which denotes the type/category of the task. It is used in order to classify similar tasks and create models for determining suitable employees based on historical task allocations. The type ID does not coincide with the unique ID that is assigned to each task instance.

Number of employees: It is possible for a task to require more than one employee.

Trade: The trade of each employee required is another parameter defined in a task. The trade, which denotes the expertise area of the employee (e.g. Electrical technician, Operator), is used for determining which employees are able to perform the task.

Duration: It is an estimated expected duration of the task in minutes. It can be defined by an expert or it can be the average duration that has been observed on past instances.

Urgency: The level of urgency is a static parameter that depends on the type of the task and shows the task's criticality level (e.g. Critical, Basic, Non-critical). It is one of the parameters used for computing the task weight dynamic parameter.

Regarding the types of tasks, the HR model developed supports both atomic and composite tasks. An atomic task includes only one execution interval whereas a composite task requires a number of heterogeneous human resources and is consisted of a number of sub-tasks/steps which have to be executed in a specific order. Consequently, each sub-task cannot be scheduled or rescheduled independently.

The static parameters required about employees are the following:

ID: A unique ID number is assigned to each employee that is used for representation in the system. Furthermore, the use of the ID instead of the employee's full name preserves privacy.

Trade: The trade indicates the expertise area of the employee. It is possible for an employee to belong to more than one trades.

Experience: The experience level of each employee is used as a parameter when scheduling tasks. Three different experience levels are defined: Trainee, Novice, Experienced. An experienced employee is expected to perform a maintenance task more effectively than a novice employee.

Shift starting/ending times: It defines the time duration in which the employee can perform tasks. Full-time working employees on the same shift share common starting/ending working times.

7.2 DYNAMIC INPUT PARAMETERS

Apart from the parameters described above, additional parameters related to tasks and employees, which are dynamic, are taken into account and are available or computed at run time.

Task weight: The task weight (or priority weight) is a numeric normalized value that shows the importance level of the task. The higher the weight the more important the task is. It is computed based on the type of the task, the urgency declared and the asset criticality.

Location of task: The execution location of a task is determined from the corresponding asset location. This parameter can be considered as dynamic in case the same task can be executed at different locations in the shop floor. The location of a given asset is defined in the gbXML schema of the shop floor. Therefore, by using this particular information an asset name can be translated into a X, Y coordination point which expresses its location, and by extension, the location of the task.

Employees' workload: Dynamic information, such as the current task and the remaining workload of each employee, is extracted from the current work schedule of the shop floor. The task list of each employee is created based on the shop floor's work schedule, after the assignment of scheduled tasks to employees has been completed. By parsing the task list of an employee, it is possible to determine whether the employee is currently busy or available, or the time intervals during which a task can be assigned to the employee. Similarly, the remaining workload of each employee in terms of busy time periods with regard to the remaining working time can be extracted. The remaining workload is expressed either as a normalized numeric value or as a discrete level belonging to one of the following: 'None', 'Low', 'Medium', 'High'.

Employees' location: Locality of the employees is another factor that is taken into account by the HR re-adaptation component, especially in cases where an urgent task of high priority has arrived and short response time to the new task is critical. In that case, the current location of each employee capable of performing the task is used in order to estimate each employee's distance to the location of the new task. The objective is to favor the selection of the employee who is closer to the task's execution location. The location of the new task is retrieved from the corresponding asset's location, as it has been previously mentioned. The HR scheduling engine supports two different approaches for employee location extraction: the sensor-based and the context-based approach.

According to the sensor-based approach, when a decision has to be made in real-time, the current location of each employee provided by the Localization Manager is utilized. The Localization Manager outputs Location events in the appropriate XML format, where each event contains localization information in terms of <X,Y> coordinates, expressed in meters, and the corresponding Tag ID. Each Tag ID is matched to an Employee ID and in this way the position of the employee in the shop floor is derived.

In case a localization infrastructure able to extract the location of an identified employee is not available, the context-based employee's location extraction approach is utilized. According to the context-based approach, the location of each employee is inferred indirectly from his/her task list. Particularly, based on the starting time set for a new task, the closest task in time in an employee's task list is considered and the employee's location is associated with that task's location. Additionally, the context-based approach is utilized in the case when a new task has to be started at a later time (not immediately), for example due to its low priority. The real-time HR engine can be configured to utilize the sensor-based localization data or to use the context-based method only. Lastly, the use of location information when assigning tasks can be disabled completely in case it is not required.

7.3 ALGORITHMIC APPROACH

In order to schedule an arriving task in real-time, the algorithm has to determine the starting time of the task and to assign the task to specific employees based on multiple criteria. By utilizing the information presented above along with the shop floor's current daily work schedule as inputs, the method constructs an updated work schedule.

7.3.1 Scheduling arriving tasks

An arriving task is usually of high priority and therefore it is important to be processed as soon as possible. A solution derived for an arriving task includes the scheduled starting time and the employeeID or employeeIDs selected to perform the task. In order to schedule a new task, the algorithm ranks the employees according to suitability for a specific starting time of the new task and evaluates the different possible solutions. Then, the solution of the minimum cost is selected and applied. Lastly, the work schedule is modified in case further arrangements are necessary, for example when an already scheduled task of low priority has to be rescheduled by updating its scheduled starting time, in order to be performed at a later time.

The component supports both hard and soft constraints that are considered in order to make decisions about task assignments. A weight is assigned to each soft constraint for defining the significance of the parameter. Rules that must not be violated derived from the company's policies and preferences are incorporated into the hard constraints which are checked first.

The dynamic HR assignment method, which utilizes the HR model presented in the previous sections, ranks the candidate employees and then selects the required employee(s) for a task. The higher the ranking of an employee, the lower the assignment cost is. The figure

below illustrates the overview of the process when a task has to be added to the work schedule. Various parameters related to human resources are considered in order to make the final decision. The suitability of each human resource (employee) is evaluated individually. The rules derived from the enterprise’s policies are combined with the output a probabilistic model and other metrics computed dynamically. The use of probabilistic models allows to utilize the produced estimations about the suitability of an employee. The models are built using historical data from past task assignments.

Figure 48 Overview of the process for scheduling arriving tasks.

One of the main factors that affect the assignment of employees is derived from the output of a Conditional Random Field (CRF) probabilistic model [16], [24], which is the probabilistic model type that is selected. CRFs are a type of discriminative undirected probabilistic graphical model and are applied in many fields (e.g. machine learning) where sequential data are available. A CRF is able to take context into account as its output at a given time step depends on a sequence of past observations. Each observation consists of a set of features, where each separate feature is a value that can affect the output. The linear chain CRF type that is utilized is an alternative to the related Hidden Markov Models (HMMs) [5], [19]. The main advantage of a CRF when compared to a HMM is the ability to include more complex non-independent features of the observations. A linear chain CRF representation is depicted in the next figure. Y_t represents the hidden state at time t , whereas X_t represents the visible associated observation at time t .

Figure 49 A linear chain CRF representation.

The probability of producing a state sequence y given an observation sequence x can be computed by the equation below:

$$p(y|x) = \frac{1}{Z(x)} \exp \left\{ \sum_{k=1}^K \lambda_k f_k(y_t, y_{t-1}, x_t) \right\}$$

where f_k is a feature function; λ_k is the learned weight associated with feature f_k ; and $Z(x)$ is the following normalization function:

$$Z(x) = \sum_y \exp \left\{ \sum_{k=1}^K \lambda_k f_k(y_t, y_{t-1}, x_t) \right\}$$

In the HR management context, a CRF model is created per each employee. The model runs online and at each time step it takes as input a feature vector (observation) and infers the hidden state. The estimation produced at each time step is the model's hidden state and in this case it can be either 0 (meaning that the corresponding employee is not recommended for the task) or 1 (meaning that the corresponding employee is candidate for the task). Furthermore, the model's belief probability of each possible state is also returned. The belief probability is a numeric value in the range [0-1]. A probability value close to the maximum for state 1 means that the specific employee is very suitable for the task. The feature vector (observation) constructed at each time step comprises the following features, normalized to [0...1]:

- the type ID of the arriving task to be assigned
- the employee's conformance to the trade required by the task
- the employee's remaining workload level

A training phase is required in advance in order to create each CRF model. A sequence of observations along with the actual ground truth label per each observation must be provided as input for learning the model parameters per each employee. The training data per model are created concurrently for all employees by using historical assignment events in the form:

< Timestamp, TaskTypeID, EmployeeIDs >

where *Timestamp* denotes the date time of the arrival of the new task with type = *TaskTypeID* and *EmployeeIDs* is the set of employees that were selected to perform the task.

The following figure illustrates the steps of the algorithm in further detail. When a new task has to be scheduled, the first step is to filter-out the employees that are incapable of performing the task due to insufficient skills (e.g. different trades). Then, a starting time for the task is set. Initially, the starting time is set to 1 minute ahead of the current time to allow an incoming task of high priority to start as soon as possible. In the next step the hard constraints are checked for eliminating the employees not satisfying the hard constraints. For instance, such a constraint applied is related to the task weight parameter. The weight of the new task and the weight of a scheduled overlapping task (if any) are compared to each other. In case

(a) $NewTaskWeight > ScheduledTaskWeight$

or for a running task

(b) $(NewTaskWeight - RunningTaskWeight) / RunningTaskWeight > 20\%$

then the particular employee is included in the candidates list. Otherwise, the employee is eliminated.

Figure 50 HR works schedule management algorithm when a new task arrives.

The feasible combinations of employees according to the human resource requirements of the arriving task are set. In case there is not any set of employees found at this step, the algorithm returns to step 2 and advances the selected starting time of the task that has to be scheduled to the expected ending time of the next task.

The total cost of each solution is computed by summing the cost of each employee required.

$$\text{Selected_employees_cost} = \text{cost}(E_1) + \text{cost}(E_2) + \dots + \text{cost}(E_n)$$

where $\text{cost}(E_i)$ is the selection cost of employee E_i and is given by:

$$\text{cost}(E_i) = W \times \text{Employee_capability_cost} + (1-W) \times \text{Employee_adaptation_cost}$$

The cost of selecting a particular employee depends on these two main factors: the capability cost and the adaptation cost. The former considers the suitability of the employee in terms of experience on the particular task, the workload assigned, and optionally, the proximity to the task. The latter considers the effect of the new task on the already scheduled tasks in the task list in case the employee is selected.

In the equation above, W is a configurable parameter in the range of 0 and 1 which defines the weights that are used in the computation. As there is a tradeoff between the capability and the adaptation cost, a value for W other than 0.5 can be set (usually between 0.4 and 0.6) in order to favor one of the two factors based on preference.

$$\text{Employee_capability_cost} =$$

$$W_1 \times (1 - P_{\text{model}}) + W_2 \times \text{RemainingWorkload} + W_3 \times \text{Distance}$$

where P_{model} is the estimated probability of selecting the employee, which is produced by the employee's CRF classifier.

The HR workload management toolkit is also able to utilize information about employees, which is provided by the semantic context Ontology Manager. The latter creates employee suitability scores in the range [0,1] based on the skills and the performance of each employee when executing each particular task. A suitability score (SS) is calculated per each EmployeeID – TaskID pair. When the HR workload management toolkit is set to utilize semantic data, it queries the ontology manager on demand in order to acquire and store the suitability scores per each employee. The query to the Ontology Manager can be re-executed when required, in order to use up-to-date information. The semantic suitability score is used complimentary to the employee's probabilistic model output and in this case, the capability cost of an employee is computed by the equation below:

Employee_capability_cost =

$$W_1 \times ((1 - P_{\text{model}}) + (1 - SS)) / 2 + W_2 \times \text{RemainingWorkload} + W_3 \times \text{Distance}$$

The estimations produced by the probabilistic models indicate the suitability of each worker to perform the arriving task, according to the task type and worker's current state and based on historical task assignment events. However, with the utilization of the semantically-enriched information, the estimation of suitability of each employee for performing a task is further enhanced due to the fact that additional parameters such as skills and performance are considered.

RemainingWorkload denotes the normalized remaining workload of the employee until the end of the shift. It is computed by dividing the total duration of remaining work in minutes by the total minutes left until the end of the shift. Remaining workload is considered in both the probabilistic model and the cost function. Only considering employee capabilities during task assignment may result in most capable employees being assigned a heavier workload [22].

Distance denotes the normalized distance [0,1] between the employee's location and the location of the new task. It is computed by dividing the Euclidean distance between the employee's location and the task's location with the maximum possible distance.

The values of the weights W_1 , W_2 and W_3 for calculating the capability cost of an employee are defined based on the selected policy. The following three different pre-defined policies are available: 'EqualWeights', 'Performance' and 'Balancing'. In all cases, W_3 is set to 0.2. When the Performance policy is applied, then $W_1 < W_2$, whereas when the Balancing policy is applied, then $W_2 < W_1$ as shown in the following table.

Policy	W ₁	W ₂	W ₃
EqualWeights	0.4	0.4	0.2
Performance	0.3	0.5	0.2
Balancing	0.5	0.3	0.2

Table 5 Weight values used per each policy.

The Employee_adaptation_cost takes into account the amount of overlap ($E_{overlap}$) with an already scheduled task, the priority weight difference between them ($E_{priority}$), and the interruption factor (E_{task_inter}) in case a task is running and has to be suspended. The latter introduces additional cost when a task with short estimated remaining has to be suspended in order to perform the new task and equals to the elapsed execution time of the currently running task divided by its estimated duration. $E_{overlap}$ is defined as the ratio the arriving task is overlapped (based on its scheduled starting time and estimated duration) by the employee's running and scheduled tasks. The Employee_adaptation_cost is considered in order to limit the number of frequent and heavy changes in employees' task lists, as frequent changes usually cause frustration to employees. When an employee is available for the whole time period during which the arriving task is planned to be performed, his adaptation cost is equal to 0.

$$\text{Employee_adaptation_cost} = (E_{overlap} + E_{priority} + E_{task_inter}) / 3$$

After evaluating the different solutions found, the solution of the minimum cost is finally selected, and as a last step the work schedule is updated. The task list of each employee is constructed based on the shop floor's work schedule, in order to compute the metrics per employee previously described. It is worth noting that it is possible to not be able to insert an arriving job to the daily schedule in extreme cases, for example, when the corresponding employees are busy performing jobs of higher priority. Regarding the probabilistic model per each employee, it can be updated on a daily basis by adding the data of the past day.

As industrial shop floors are dynamic complex environments, there may be short tasks that have to be performed from time to time that are of very low priority. In that case, these tasks may not be included in the daily work schedule. However, as these tasks are of very low priority, they can be interrupted at any time in case of a new task arrival and be resumed at a later time with no cost. Therefore, an employee performing such a task can be considered available.

7.3.2 Workload balancing monitoring

Workload balancing is a critical functionality in various different fields such as application distribution in supercomputing systems and task distribution to human resources. In the latter case, morale issues can arise when some team members carry heavier workload than the

other members of the team. Thus, it is important to efficiently manage the workload of each individual employee in order to keep each employee satisfied at the end of the shift. The workload balancing monitoring module of the HR scheduling engine periodically monitors the assigned workload to the employees of each trade in order to detect imbalances that are above a preferred threshold. If this is the case, the module can automatically re-assign a scheduled task to another employee who is also capable of performing it in order to balance the workload. Furthermore, the workload balancing functionality is applied after a change has occurred in the work schedule of the shop floor, such an addition of a new task. Even if the remaining workload is taken into account when assigning a new task to an employee, as previously presented, workload imbalance can still occur depending on the current status of each employee.

In general, the three workload balancing steps are the following ([29]):

1. Imbalance evaluation
2. Decide how to balance if needed
3. Redistribute work to correct the imbalance

These steps define when and how to perform the workload balancing process. Workload balance metrics characterize how unevenly work is distributed. The percent imbalance metric PWI, which is used, measures the severity of workload imbalance and is defined as:

$$PWI = (L_{MAX} / L_{AVG} - 1) \times 100\%$$

where L_{MAX} is the maximum workload observed and L_{AVG} is the average workload assigned to the employees of the same trade.

Standard deviation is another metric that can be used for evaluating the workload imbalance:

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=0}^n (L_i - L_{AVG})^2}{n}}$$

where n is the number of employees and L_i is the workload of the i^{th} employee.

The implemented workload balancing approach includes five steps which are described next. Initially, the workload assigned per each employee is calculated by summing the duration of all tasks in the employee's task list. The criticality level (three different levels) of a task is also taken into account, as a critical task is considered to be more demanding for an employee. The next step determines whether task re-assignment is necessary by computing the imbalance metric (PWI) for each group of employees of the same trade and checking if it exceeds the preferred threshold. The value of the threshold determines the sensitivity of the module and the frequency of task re-assignments. If workload balancing has to be applied, the employee with the highest workload is selected. Then, the system selects the task to be re-assigned, which must be in the 'Scheduled' status. Tasks of lower priority are preferred, as well as the tasks with the latest starting time. At the next step, the module selects the employee to whom the task will be re-assigned. It exports a list of candidate employees who

are available to perform the task and ranks them in ascending order with regard to workload and with regard to the number of their new task assignments that occurred during the working hours. The latter metric is monitored per each employee and is updated when either a new task is assigned to an employee or an already scheduled task is re-assigned to a different employee. Lastly, right after the determination of the proposed task re-assignment, imbalance is evaluated again and compared to the initially computed imbalance value. The task re-assignment action is applied if the resulting imbalance is lower than the one that was initially computed. The steps of the workload balancing process are depicted in the figure below.

Figure 51 Flowchart of the workload balancing process.

It is worth mentioning that the workload balancing module has been designed considering that it employs human resources. As a result, multiple concurrent task re-assignments should be avoided in order not to cause confusion to managers and workers.

To sum up, the work schedule management and HR re-adaptation method that has been developed in the context of Satisfactory has several advantages. It is light on computational resources as the time required in order to find a solution is short. This is due to the fact that the search that is performed is heuristic and not exhaustive. However, the algorithm can be easily modified in order to evaluate a larger number of possible solutions when scheduling a new task, at the expense of increased computational time. Furthermore, the method utilizes historical data in order to rank human resources according to competence using

personalized models. Lastly, the method takes into account the changes that can be introduced when a new task has to be scheduled, by computing the adaptation cost.

7.4 OUTPUT EVALUATION (KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS)

The adaptation of the shop floor's work schedule has the potential to increase the performance and the throughput (number of tasks completed per day). However, since in this case the main processing units are human resources instead of machines, frequent changes in the task list of each employee causes discomfort and confusion. Thus, the allocation decisions must be able to keep the balance between the level of employees' satisfaction and the efficient operation of the shop floor (response to the workload demand). A Key Performance Indicator (KPI) is a type of performance measurement, which shows how effectively an organization is achieving key business objectives. A metric for evaluating the feasibility of a daily work schedule is the number of finished tasks at the end of the shift with regard to the total number of scheduled tasks (excluding the cases of unfinished tasks due to unpredicted exceptions, such as malfunctions). Moreover, the acceptance rate of the automatically generated task assignments or the work schedule changes is a metric that shows whether the manager is satisfied by the provided output. Frequent manual edits of the work schedule after automated decisions indicate that the latter are not the expected or the optimal.

As the work schedule of the shop floor is stored into the Satisfactory repository on change in XML format, historical data are available showing how the work schedule had evolved over time. Through the analysis of the historical information, the aforementioned performance indicators can be calculated. Furthermore, the models that are used to estimate the suitability of each employee can be updated on a daily basis or on demand, by parsing the historical work schedule events stored in the database.

8 CONCLUSIONS

We described how the proposed toolkit can effectively boost the efficiency and the quality of work in the Industry 4.0. We detailed how the Satisfactory functionalities can provide significant benefits in terms of both machinery and workers' management.

The visualization toolkit provides an intuitive interface which gives the possibility to manage a factory by collecting alarms, notifications and anomalous behaviors in a single entity. This allows for a prompt reaction to a wide set of events thus re-adapting the work schedule to better suit unforeseen needs and constraints.

The functionality provided by the work schedule management toolkit results in the automated distribution and balancing of the workload according to the factory's policies applied, performance metrics and fairness. Efficient initial work schedules can be created based on the available human resources and open tasks. Furthermore, the re-adaptation of the assigned human resources when new unexpected tasks arrive or when it is required, is also applicable. The HR scheduling and workload balancing engine allows the end user to set the weights of the criteria on which the decisions are made according to their individual business objectives. Additionally, the selection of the most appropriate employee to perform a task is enhanced based on the results from ontology queries, capitalizing on the semantically-enriched framework.

This document has been updated according to the project's schedule in order to reflect the planned improvements and implementations over the lifespan of task 2.4. This is the last version of this document that describes some of the modules that form the Satisfactory ecosystem. The data collection in the pilots is still ongoing and minor modifications to the described component could happen. If these changes will occur, they will be reflected in deliverable D6.5 with screencasts as user manuals.

In the followings the list of repositories of the described software components, intellectual propriety of ISMB under GNU PUBLIC LICENCE version2 licensing.

- source code
 - <svn://ITI-292.iti.gr:3690/SatisfactoryProject/WP2/ISMB/ReAdaptationToolkit>
 - <svn://ITI-292.iti.gr:3690/SatisfactoryProject/WP2/ISMB/DigitalAndon>
 - <svn://ITI-292.iti.gr:3690/SatisfactoryProject/WP2/ISMB/MessageBoard>
 - <svn://ITI-292.iti.gr:3690/SatisfactoryProject/WP3/ISMB/DigitalAndonSt>
- binaries
 - <svn://ITI-292.iti.gr:3690/SatisfactoryProject/WP3/ISMB/GCRMConsole>
 - <svn://ITI-292.iti.gr:3690/SatisfactoryProject/WP3/ISMB/MultipleMediaManager>

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ANNEX

1. An excerpt of the work schedule of the day according to the CIDEM compatible XML format

```

<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<CIDEM xmlns:SFcommon="http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/common"
xmlns:b2mml="http://www.mesa.org/xml/B2MML-V0600">
  <ShopFloor>
    <ShopFloorID>CPERI</ShopFloorID>
    <SFEvents>
      <EventList>
        <Event>
          <ID>1488992400</ID>
          <Type>Procedure</Type>
          <TimeStamp>2017-03-08T19:00:00.000</TimeStamp>
          <Space>CPERI</Space>
          <Content>
            <Maintenance>
              <WorkScheduleList>
                <b2mml:ID>1</b2mml:ID>
                <b2mml:Description>24 hours work schedule for CPERI shop-floor</b2mml:Description>
                <b2mml:PublishedDate>2017-03-08T19:00:00.000</b2mml:PublishedDate>
                <b2mml:WorkRequest>
                  <b2mml:ID>112118</b2mml:ID>
                  <b2mml:Description>Burned resistance JE201 on the injector</b2mml:Description>
                  <b2mml:WorkType>Maintenance</b2mml:WorkType>
                  <b2mml:StartTime>2017-03-08T09:00:00.000</b2mml:StartTime>
                  <b2mml:EndTime>2017-03-08T09:30:00.000</b2mml:EndTime>
                  <b2mml:JobOrder>
                    <b2mml:ID>1121181</b2mml:ID>
                    <b2mml:Description>Burned resistance JE201 on the injector</b2mml:Description>
                    <b2mml:WorkType>Maintenance</b2mml:WorkType>
                    <b2mml:StartTime>2017-03-08T09:00:00.000</b2mml:StartTime>
                    <b2mml:EndTime>2017-03-08T09:30:00.000</b2mml:EndTime>
                    <b2mml:Priority>1</b2mml:Priority>
                    <b2mml:PersonnelRequirement>
                      <b2mml:PersonID>14</b2mml:PersonID>
                      <b2mml:Description>Automation Technician</b2mml:Description>
                    </b2mml:PersonnelRequirement>
                    <b2mml:EquipmentRequirement>
                      <b2mml:Description>None</b2mml:Description>
                    </b2mml:EquipmentRequirement>
                    <b2mml:PhysicalAssetRequirement>
                      <b2mml:PhysicalAssetClassID>F-FCC-RI</b2mml:PhysicalAssetClassID>
                      <b2mml:Description/>
                    </b2mml:PhysicalAssetRequirement>
                    <b2mml:MaterialRequirement>
                      <b2mml:Description>None</b2mml:Description>
                    </b2mml:MaterialRequirement>
                  </b2mml:JobOrder>
                </b2mml:WorkRequest>
              </b2mml:WorkScheduleList>
            </b2mml:Content>
          </b2mml:Event>
        </b2mml:EventList>
      </b2mml:SFEvents>
    </b2mml:ShopFloor>
  </b2mml:CIDEM>

```


2. Description and requirements of a new maintenance job that has to be scheduled, in the appropriate XML format

```

<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<CIDEM xmlns:b2mml="http://www.mesa.org/xml/B2MML-V0600">
  <ShopFloor>
    <ShopFloorID>CPERI</ShopFloorID>
    <SFEvents>
      <EventList>
        <Event>
          <ID>1</ID>
          <Type>NewJob</Type>
          <TimeStamp>2017-04-06T10:05:30</TimeStamp>
          <Space>BIOCAT</Space>
          <SourceID>BIOCAT.TE101A</SourceID>
          <Content>
            <ReAdaptation>
              <JobsList>
                <NewJob>
                  <b2mml:WorkRequest>
                    <b2mml:ID>112120</b2mml:ID>
                    <b2mml:Description>FCC Oil WTM-2 Replacement</b2mml:Description>
                    <b2mml:WorkType>Maintenance</b2mml:WorkType>
                    <b2mml:WorkTypeID>4</b2mml:WorkTypeID>
                    <b2mml:Score>80</b2mml:Score>
                    <b2mml:Duration>PT120M</b2mml:Duration>
                    <b2mml:JobOrder>
                      <b2mml:ID>112120</b2mml:ID>
                      <b2mml:Description>FCC Oil WTM-2 Replacement</b2mml:Description>
                      <b2mml:WorkType>Maintenance</b2mml:WorkType>
                      <b2mml:Duration>PT120M</b2mml:Duration>
                      <b2mml:Priority>1</b2mml:Priority>
                      <b2mml:PersonnelRequirement>
                        <b2mml:Description>Electrical Technician</b2mml:Description>
                      </b2mml:PersonnelRequirement>
                      <b2mml:EquipmentRequirement>
                        <b2mml:Description>None</b2mml:Description>
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                      <b2mml:PhysicalAssetRequirement>
                        <b2mml:PhysicalAssetClassID>F-FCC-RI</b2mml:PhysicalAssetClassID>
                      </b2mml:PhysicalAssetRequirement>
                      <b2mml:MaterialRequirement>
                        <b2mml:Description>None</b2mml:Description>
                      </b2mml:MaterialRequirement>
                    </b2mml:JobOrder>
                  </b2mml:WorkRequest>
                </NewJob>
              </JobsList>
            </ReAdaptation>
          </Content>
        </Event>
      </EventList>
    </SFEvents>
  </ShopFloor>
</CIDEM>

```